
Life cycle assessment of hydrogen production: Comparison between renewable energy-based electrolysis and steam reforming

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Report abstract

Aiming for a global decarbonisation of energy services, hydrogen energy, as a potentially ‘green’ energy vector, gives a cross-boundary opportunity for the sustainable and renewable global energy landscape transition. But rarely of the research on H₂ production environmental performance focus on national or regional level’s average resource availability and technological market shares. While such results could however provide the scientific basis to guide one nation’s financing policy formulation, subsidies determination and tender process with the aim to promote the penetration of renewable and low-carbon H₂ into the society. And some important impact categories like eutrophication potential, human toxicity potential, ionizing radiation, photochemical Oxidation Potential, are seldomly discussed in the existing literatures on H₂ production, which is the same for the resources use mineral and metals, abiotic Depletion Potential, and water consumption. Besides, no research could be found by the writer than perform a detail and holistic sensitivity and uncertainty analysis regarding all the foreground and background life cycle parameters involved in the H₂ production life cycle. And rarely of the sensitivity and uncertainty analysis in H₂ production environmental impact assessment focus on the parameters in CCS process combined with H₂ production.

From the angle of the average resource availability and technology market share in France in 2019, this research analyze and compare the environmental influence of methane reforming H₂ production technology and water electrolysis H₂ production with renewable electricity. With the corresponding parametric life cycle assessment model built in BW2 based *lca_algebraic* library, towards 11 impact categories, this research performs the first detail and holistic sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis regarding all the foreground and background life cycle parameters involved in the H₂ production life cycle. 12 methane reforming H₂ production pathway and 4 pathway of water electrolysis H₂ production with renewable electricity were analysed base on different technical details and life cycle hypothesis. According to the impact categories score interpretation based on unit process contribution, findings discovered from comparison with other research results, as well as sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis, this research also propose the guidelines and suggestions towards improving the life cycle sustainability of H₂ production pathways analysed.

The structure of this research is arranged as follows: Chapter 1 state in detail the vision and research activities in the host laboratory of this research internship. Following in Chapter 1 systemically show the literature review regarding H₂, current H₂ production states in EU and France as well as current French national policies aiming for low-carbon and renewable H₂ penetration improvement. Chapter 1 end with a comprehensive review of the environmental impact assessment researches towards H₂ production technology, where the shortage of existing researches is holistically revealed. Chapter 2 elaborate the life cycle assessment methodology applied by this research as means for H₂ production environmental impact assessment. Following the life cycle assessment methodology, Chapter 2 state in detail the goal and scope definition, hypothesis and method for life cycle inventory analysis, life cycle impact assessment, as well as the life cycle result interpretation for each H₂ production pathway analysed. The method for localizing the LCI to current French context to represent average resource availability and technology market share in France in 2019, as well as the hypothesis and method for holistic sensitivity analysis and uncertainty analysis regarding all the foreground and background life cycle parameters involved in the H₂ production life cycle is carefully elaborate in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 systemically show the discussion on the life cycle assessment result: the hotspot unit process in each impact categories score, findings discovered from comparison with other research results, as well as impact categories score’s sensitivity to life cycle parameters and corresponding impact categories score uncertainty. Base on the researches performed, the Chapter 4 propose the guidelines and suggestions towards improving the life cycle sustainability of H₂ production pathways analysed.

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Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the Host Laboratory

1.1.1 Location, vision, goals

Located in Sophia Antipolis technology park, the host laboratory of the internship, the Centre Observation, Impacts, Energy (O.I.E centre) is a thriving centre with high scientific vitality established on the 1st January 2013. The O.I.E Centre is a joint MINES ParisTech - ARMINES research team, whose activities are located at the crossroads of energy, the environment and Earth observation. Based on basic & applied science disciplines (mathematics, metrology, physics, environment, etc.) and information & communication technology, it conducts research on the environmental impact and the resource evaluation of renewable energy sources as well as their development at spatial and temporal levels¹. Database and Web services are among the main knowledge dissemination tools of the centre^{2-4, 11111}.

1.1.2 Research activities

As indicated by the centre's name, the main research interests of O.I.E team are in the field of Earth observation, assessment of energy sectors' environmental impacts, and the assessment and modelling of renewable energy resources.

In the field of Earth observation, the centre has acquired academically and industrially recognized knowledge and skills particularly in data fusion and change detection. The SoDa service², a collaborative platform dedicated to solar radiation, launched in 2002 by O.I.E centre, offers open, standard, and interoperable access to various applications and databases provided by O.I.E. centre or other institutes and companies around the world. There are more than 150 million data request to SoDa data service in 2020².

For the environmental impact assessment of energy technologies, the centre mainly focuses on the following 4 aspects:

- Spatial modelling of energy generation systems and their environmental impacts by life cycle assessment (LCA).

As a long-term research effort, tackled in collaboration with other teams in France and in Europe, O.I.E centre integrates geographic aspects in order to assess spatially characterized environmental impacts for industrial sectors and products in the energy field. This spatialization of impacts is materialized by the creation of web services for renewable sectors with, for example, a service for the international energy agency (IEA) for the photovoltaic sector: ENVI-PV⁵.

- Integration of uncertainties in LCA studies.

O.I.E centre has developed a framework that helps to integrate all the uncertainties and variability associated with input parameters in life cycle inventories, so as to understand their effect on the environmental impact results assessed. The methodological framework developed at O.I.E centre also allows the identification of key determining factors to each environmental impact result, which can serve to support decision-making in terms of location selection, technological choices, industrial chain's environmental impact optimization.

- LCA of innovative technologies

The biomass sector, embodied with strong carbon neutrality potential, is also addressed at O.I.E centre. In order to promote the decarbonization of processes and fuels, sustainability assessment of algae cultivation and related bioenergy extraction system becomes one of the main research interests of the centre. The O.I.E centre also develops inventories for other advanced technological options for sustainable production, such as photovoltaic systems integrating solar radiation reflection elements (the shape of mirrors) to improve efficiency and environmental performance.

- Links between LCA and energy scenarios.

O.I.E centre will continue the assessment of the prospective energy scenarios for 2030 and 2050 as well as the analysis of the environmental effects linked to possible technical and political contexts.

For the assessment and modelling of renewable energy resources, the centre mainly focuses on 2 hotspots:

- Solar radiation prediction

O.I.E centre contributes to the research and development of methods for processing observations made by satellites to estimate the solar illumination available on the ground. In partnership with DLR (German aerospace centre). O.I.E centre develops the Heliosat-5 method. The centre continues the operational application of previous Heliosat versions in collaboration with the Transvalor Ltd., in order to create or update databases of solar radiation, called HelioClim.

-Resource assessment under the climate change.

The resource assessment activities of the centre in the consideration of climate change are recent and essentially take place in the framework of the European Climate Change Service Copernicus Service (C3S).

In the future, the centre will continue to contribute to the transformation of the energy system & society by a consistent monitoring and assessing of the climate, environment, and renewable energy resources; the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the renewable energy industry chains.

Figure 1.1: Aerial view of the MINES ParisTech in Sophia Antipolis

1.2 Mission and context of the internship

In current global techno-economic context, where fossil fuels, e.g., coal, natural gas, cover 80 % of the global energy consumption⁶, the steady increase of the world's energy demand and the rise of greenhouse gas emissions keep pressuring the world's sustainable development⁷. As a potentially renewable energy carrier, hydrogen (H₂) could be a pillar of the world's energy transition^{8, 9}. In a context of unprecedented political and business momentum, the number of policies and projects for clean and renewable hydrogen around the world are expanding rapidly¹⁰.

The French government has established the "hydrogen deployment plan for the energy transition¹¹" and national energy and climate plan^{11, 12} (NECP). According to this plan, France will switch from 20 % to 40 % of fossil-based hydrogen in industry to renewable hydrogen electrolysed from low carbon electricity or recovered from biomass by 2028, to fulfil the ever-rising H₂ demand⁹.

With robust actors in the fields of hydrogen and fuel cells from both industry (AirLiquide, Michelin, McPhy, etc.) and research/academia (CEA, CNRS), under a clear vision, the ever-increasing investment in hydrogen deployment has enabled France as a thriving hydrogen economic market. The new facilities and technologies, either demonstration or commercial, keep emerging, where the renewable electrolyzed H₂ and biomass sourced H₂ pathways draw the main focus of the society due to their renewable and sustainable potential.

The main objective of the internship is a comprehensive environmental impact investigation and comparison among H₂ production pathways. In the context of average French resource availability and technology market share, the focus is mainly put on H₂ production pathways of natural gas and bi-methane vapor reforming as well as water electrolysis from renewable energy.

The study investigated the following specific research targets:

- From the angle of the average French resource availability and technology market share, identify the H₂ production pathways to be analysed

- To calculate the environmental impacts, identify the main contributors and hotspot (i.e., foreground and background activities and emissions) of each impact category for all H₂ production pathways analysed.
- To analyse and present the results of uncertainties propagation in all H₂ production pathways analysed.
- To analyse and present the importance of each parameters uncertainty in the global uncertainty of each impact category for H₂ production pathways analysed.
- To compare the result with other research, comment on and put forward the guidelines and suggestions improving the life cycle sustainability of H₂ production pathways analysed.

1.3 Literature review

The ever-increasing energy demand worldwide, mainly in the form of fossil fuel demand, becomes the main driver of global warming⁶, environment degradation^{13, 14} and human disease^{15, 16}. Aiming for a global decarbonisation of energy services, hydrogen energy, as a potentially ‘green’ energy vector, gives a cross-boundary opportunity for the sustainable and renewable global energy landscape transition^{8, 9}. Clean and renewable hydrogen projects and the corresponding policies are increasingly put in place in more and more countries^{10, 17}.

1.3.1 Hydrogen and hydrogen sector in France

1.3.1.1 Hydrogen

Hydrogen, as the lightest element in Mendeleev’s periodic table, present from the first moment of the universe and takes around 75% of the total mass of the universe¹⁸. Colorless, odorless and non-corrosive, hydrogen gas, i.e., the hydrogen molecule (H₂), is a good energy carrier on Earth, and has a higher mass energy density (120MJ/kg) compared to fossil fuels^{18, 19}. However, due to its light molecular weight, atmospheric equilibrium H₂ occupies a much larger space than fossil fuels. For this reason, in real applications such as fuel cells in car and electricity generation, H₂ needs to be compressed to a high pressure (700 bar or 350 bar) to increase its volumetric energy density. This property is causing inconvenience for the transportation and storage of hydrogen energy.

To face the concerns related to anthropogenic global warming, researchers identified that, H₂, if largely produced with renewable and sustainable source, e.g., the biomass gasification^{20, 21}, bio-CH₄ vaporizing reforming^{22, 23} and renewable electrolysis of water^{24, 25}, can become the energy carrier that will contribute to achieving a global carbon-neutral sustainable society.

1.3.1.2 Policies for a national hydrogen economy

In the National energy and climate plans (NECP) of France, the country set the target of 36 % CO₂ emission reduction by 2030 compared to 2005²⁶, and aims to achieve a carbon-neutral society by 2050²⁷. France also declares in its “Law on Energy Transition for Green Growth²⁸” that, compared to 2012, the country will reduce its final energy consumption by 7 % in 2023 and 14% by 2028. In addition, it plans to reduce its fossil fuels consumption by 20% in 2023 and 35% by 2028. The country also aims to decrease its nuclear energy to less than 50% of the total electricity production by 2035²⁸.

The hydrogen economy in France is developing fast. France identified hydrogen as an indispensable vector on the way to a zero-emission transportation and a carbon neutral French society²⁹. The Multiannual Energy Program (the “PPE”) released on 23rd April 2020 (for the periods 2019-2023 and 2024-2028), provides a basket of policy that add financial support for the hydrogen sector³⁰. Under the instruction of the PPE 2020, guarantees of origin scheme(GOs) and Guarantees of Traceability (GT), as has already been applied to the French biogas market, will also be developed³⁰. Ordinance No. 2021-167 published by the French government³¹, defines the future context of the renewable and low-carbon hydrogen market in the country. All these measures will finally standardise the co-financing models for H₂ ecosystem deployment that integrate different uses (mobility, industry, etc.) up to the local level in France. France also participated in the HyLaw project, IPCEI projects etc,³²⁻³⁵ to identify, assess, and find prioritizing measures to the major regulatory barriers, and thus to accelerate the development of a global hydrogen market.

1.3.1.3 Hydrogen production

Hydrogen, either in France, Europe or globally, basing on the purpose of usage, could be defined as 3 types: captive H₂, by-product H₂, and merchant H₂^{8, 36, 37}. The ammonia, oil-refining, and petrochemical

industry, consume large amounts of H₂ produced by a dedicated H₂ unit within their industrial facilities. This kind of H₂, produced for their own company's use without selling to a third party, is called captive H₂. When the H₂ produced is specifically for selling to a third party, the H₂ is called merchant H₂. The by-product H₂ refers to the H₂ unintentionally produced from one process intent to produce another product, e.g., the H₂ generated from the coke oven process, electrolysis to produce chlorine and sodium chlorate, and petrochemicals process, etc³⁷.

Figure 1.2: H₂ production share of the European Economic Area (EU-27 plus the UK, Norway, Switzerland and Iceland) in 2018 ³⁸

At present, Europe currently consumes 339 TWh H₂ per year in total³⁹, in which around 90.6% is fossil-based hydrogen⁴⁰. In Europe 2018, only two fossil-based hydrogen production plant were using carbon capture (CCS) technologies. Around 920,000 metric tons (Mt) H₂ were produced in France in 2008³⁷. The captive H₂, merchant H₂, by-product H₂ reach a production capacity of 1123.3 Mt/day, 311.5 Mt/day, 654 Mt/day for France 2019⁴¹. Almost all merchant H₂ is produced from steam methane reforming and, to a lower extent, autothermal reforming (ATR) and less commonly partial oxidation (POX), both in Europe^{8, 39} and France^{37,41}. For water electrolysis H₂ with low carbon or renewable electricity, their total installed capacity of electrolyser is around 58MW EU27 2018 ³⁸, and around half of the electrolysis unit is in Germany. 58 MW electrolyser produce less than 0.1% of total H₂ production capacity in Europe. However, as discussed above, renewable and low-carbon H₂ should take the majority of the captive and merchant H₂ market in France and Europe, to achieve the successful renewable and sustainable energy transition.

Under the stimulus promotion policies, school, laboratory, and enterprise are actively carry out research, demonstration, and commercialization of the renewable and low-carbon H₂ production technologies. For wind powered electrolysis H₂ production, in collaboration with Chantiers de l'Atlantique, Lhyfe ⁴² will start to operate world's first commercialized off-shore wind hydrogen production plant at the coast of Le Croisic since 2022⁴³. Installed at the demonstration site, the electrolyser is connected to various marine renewable energy sources including floating wind turbine. The companies are also designing a new off-shore hydrogen production platform with aiming capacities changing from tens to several hundred MW, which will be installed in Saint-Nazaire around 2024.

For solar powered electrolysis H₂ production, announced in January 2021, TotalEnergies and ENGIE have signed the cooperation agreement for Masshylvia project ⁴⁴, to design, develop, build, and operate France's currently largest renewable hydrogen production program in Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur South region. The Masshylvia project will be powered by solar farms with a total capacity of more than 40 MW electrolyzers to meet the H₂ requirement of a biorefinery plant nearby. 15 tonnes of renewable H₂ will be produced every day starting in 2024. The "HyGreen Provence" ⁴⁵ project initiated by ENGIE and Air Liquide with the Durance, Luberon, Verdon urban area (DLVA), aims to produce, store, and distribute renewable hydrogen for solar electricity electrolysis in the area to meet the mobility, heating, cooling, and industry need both locally and regionally. Tens of thousands metric tons of renewable hydrogen will be produced since 2024, thus to contribute to the zero-carbon transition of the region. Lhyfe also coordinated the 10 phase VHyGO project⁴⁶ aims to democratization the renewable H₂ to general public, thus building a complete renewable hydrogen ecosystem for the west regions (Brittany,

Normandy and Loire Valley). Starting by construction 3.5MW electrolyser, VHyGO project is going to produce least 5 tonnes of renewable hydrogen per day at 10 different sites by 2024 and lowering the price of renewable H₂ to 8 € /kg in 2030. Aiming to decarbonate industrial activities (refining and chemical) on the Seine Valley axis in Normandy, Air Liquide invest in the H2V Normandy project⁴⁵ to build renewable and low-carbon hydrogen that up to 200 MW. Besides, CEA and partners announced the formation of Genvia Ltd., on 11st Jan 2021, to accelerate the commercialization of the first fully reversible high-temperature solid oxide electrolysis technology ^{47, 48} embodied with extremely high efficiency and cost-effectiveness. More renewable water electrolysis H₂ production project across Europe can be found on the website of Fuel Cell and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking ⁴⁹, IEA ⁵⁰, and EU Commission ⁵¹.

For biomass-sourced H₂ production pathway, H₂ produced by biomass gasification will occupy most of the biomass-sourced H₂ market in EU4 country (Germany, France, Scandinavia, and UK) ⁵². And biomass gasification H₂ production is currently the most commercialized pathway in France⁵³. Haffner Energy⁵⁴ developed the Hynoca process to thermolysis the biomass into syngas and, after purification, becomes H₂. The process is further developed by VitroHydrogenic consortium to become a high efficient process which can recover up to 70% of the biomass energy and bring down the prize of H₂: € 6/kg⁵⁵. The first demonstration of Hynoca H₂ production process started in Vitry-le-François 2019 and will last for 4 years ⁵⁶, reaching a productivity of 120 kg H₂ /500 tonnes wood pellets. The second demonstration of Hynoca H₂ production process is carried in Strasbourg to power around 50 buses every day starting from 2021 ⁵⁷. Haffner Energy aims to lower the prize of the Hynoca process to € 3/kg in 2025. Developed by Enosis in Toulouse and funded by ENGIE, the Wood-Hy project ⁵⁸ produce renewable H₂ through gasification of crushing wood from the pines in the Landes forest. Started at 2022, Wood-Hy project will reach 1,000 tonnes annual H₂ production rate to power more than 5,000 vehicles ⁵⁹.

Regarding bio-CH₄ reforming H₂ production, by 2020 AirLiquide committed to produce at least 50% of the company's total H₂ productivity with carbon-neutral process through a combination of biogas reforming, water electrolysis with renewable energy, emitted gas recover during the natural gas production process ⁶⁰. The technology readiness level (TRL) for other biomass-sourced H₂ production pathways in France is currently low ⁶¹. Most of the research for relatively new technologies, e.g., biomass fermentation H₂ production ⁶²⁻⁶⁴, bioethanol and bio-oil reforming H₂ production ⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷, bio-CH₄ plasma pyrolysis H₂ production ^{68, 69} are still under laboratory and pilot scale development and research.

1.3.2 Environmental impact assessment of hydrogen production

On the way to global decarbonisation of the energy sectors, identifying the sustainable H₂ production pathways using environmental impact assessment of H₂ production has been long a hot spot for researchers. Life Cycle Assessment methodology (detailed explained in Section 2.1), which aims for assessing potential environmental impacts associated with all life cycle stages (e.g., extraction and processing of raw material, manufacture, distribution and use, recycling, or end-of-life treatment) of a commercial product, process, or service, is widely accepted and developed by the researchers working on environmental impact assessment of H₂ production.

In terms of methodological innovation, Valente et al. ⁷⁰⁻⁷² developed an approach for a widely accepted, harmonized approach to estimate the environmental impacts of H₂ production, currently using three impact categories: the global warming potential (GWP), cumulative energy demand (CED), and acidification potential (AP). Their harmonized LCA method has been applied to a vast of electrochemical ⁷³, thermochemical⁷¹, nuclear ⁷⁴, and biological⁷⁵ H₂ production pathway. In their harmonization protocol to refining a cradle-to-gate system boundaries, they suggest a functional unit of 1 kg industrial grade hydrogen (purity >99%) and compressed to 200 bars. To increase comparability of the results, they suggest to use system expansion or economic allocation in the attributional LCA assessment when hydrogen is the main product or by-product, respectively⁷⁰. Including the capital goods and H₂ compression stages under the harmonized LCA framework, will generally lead to an increase of GWP, CED⁷¹, and AP⁷² compared to the result in original literatures. Due to the different nature of life-cycle indicators, Valente et al. ⁷⁰⁻⁷² confirm the strong correlation between high GWP and CED (nuclear electrolysis pathway no included), but negates the correlation between GWP and AP.

However, for a region or a country like France who aim to implement a highly sustainable H₂ sector, for sure that there will be massive production for different renewable and low-carbon H₂ production technologies feed by different feedstocks along with continuous development of the industry. Current environmental impact assessment of H₂ production technologies rarely focus on national or regional

level's average resource availability and technological market shares. Such results could, however, provide the scientific basis to guide one nation's financing policy formulation³¹, subsidies determination⁷⁶ and tender process⁷⁷ with the aim to promote the penetration of renewable and low-carbon H₂ into the society.

For example, Al-Qahtani et al.,⁷⁸ propose a six step approach to calculate and convert all the endpoint environmental impact of H₂ production into monetary value, thus to get the total cost of hydrogen (TCOH) containing the levelized cost of H₂ production and monetary value to eliminate environmental externalities of corresponding H₂ production life cycle. Performing the lacked research stated above, and combined it with the TCOH method of Qahtani et al.,⁷⁸ we can provide a scientific recommendation of the subsidies amount and tender prize that can deliver to one specific low-carbon H₂ project, or the amount of the environmental externalities tax needed to put on the fossil-based H₂ producer to stimulate the sustainable transition of the H₂ sector in one country.

Regarding specific technologies, embodied with huge sustainability potential, the environmental performance of water electrolysis H₂ production has been extensively studied^{24, 79-81}. Types of electricity used in the water electrolysis process is the determining factor for the environmental impact of the H₂ produced^{24, 70, 78, 82}. The majority of the research agrees that H₂ from wind, solar, and hydro electrolysis generally has a lower GWP, CED, and AP than the biomass sourced H₂ and much lower than the fossil-based H₂ without CCS^{24, 70-72, 80}. In terms of GWP, CED, and AP, hydro electrolysis ranked as the best among water electrolysis H₂ pathways, which is followed by wind electrolysis, photovoltaic solar electrolysis, and thermal solar ranked as the worst^{24, 70, 72, 80}. However, some important impact categories like eutrophication potential (EP), human toxicity potential (HTP), ionizing radiation (IR), photochemical Oxidation Potential (POFP), are seldomly discussed in the existing literatures on water electrolysis and biomass-sourced H₂ production, which is the same for the resources use mineral and metals (MD), abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP), and water consumption²⁴. But these impact categories are very important, which are not supposed to be neglected.

For biomass sourced H₂ production LCA, most of the research focuses on the biomass gasification technologies. LCA on bioethanol, bio-oil, bio-CH₄ reforming, fermentation process and water electrolysis powered by fuel from biomass gasification can also be found^{24, 79-81}. Majority of the research shows that, for GWP and CED, biomass gasification performs the best and is comparable to water electrolysis powered by fuel from biomass gasification, which is followed by biofuel reforming process. And biomass fermentation process (except dark fermentation, whose life cycle GWP and CED is extremely high) is generally comparable to the biofuel reforming process. Bioethanol reforming H₂ production generally has the lowest life cycle GWP and CED among the biofuel reforming process, which is followed by bio-oil and bio-CH₄ reforming process. For AP, biomass gasification pathways generally perform better than biofuel reforming process, however, bio-CH₄ reforming can reach a negative AP (much lower than the performance of biomass gasification pathways) if the bio-CH₄ feedstock is considered as burden free e.g., the animal manure⁷¹. This indicates the allocation strategies about how to taking the biogas production by-product into account can hugely influence the AP potential of biogas sourced H₂. However, most of the research neglects CCS as a further decarbonisation scenario in H₂ production LCA, especially for fossil NG and bio-CH₄ reforming pathways.

Among the few research taking CCS into consideration, Susmozas et al.⁸³ indicate a huge potential to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere from biomass gasification H₂ production integrated with CCS operation using short-rotation poplar as feedstock. The environmental benefit of combining CCS with biomass gasification H₂ production, especially the negative-carbon effect, is further confirmed by Antonini et al.²⁰. Applying CCS to steam CH₄ reforming (SMR) H₂ facilities will achieve 70% to 200% GWP reduction as indicated by the few research available^{22, 84, 85}, while CCS process will increase the H₂ selling prize at around 20-60% according to the extensive techno-economic analysis^{44, 85-88}. And regarding the bio-CH₄ SMR H₂ production LCA, researchers have paid great attention on bio-CH₄ converted from animal waste and crop residues²². Biowaste (green waste, food waste and paper waste, animal processing waste etc.) sourced bio-CH₄ and sewage sludge sourced bio-CH₄ are seldomly taken as a feedstock for SMR H₂ production during a LCA study.

Regarding the uncertainty (UA) and sensitivity analysis (SA), a detailed review of UA and SA for H₂ production LCA hasn't appeared yet. Most of the UA and SA for H₂ production focus on the techno-economic context^{84, 89-98} and only few studies focus the UA and SA of H₂ production on LCA. The little

research available only focuses on the UA and SA of foreground life cycle parameters related to H₂ production facilities and process. UA and SA towards these foreground life cycle parameters has been carried out: reduction and recycling rate of electrolysis stack material⁹⁹; electrolyser efficiency¹⁰⁰; energy mix used during H₂ production¹⁰¹; allocation strategy¹⁰² and treatment of H₂ production by-product¹⁰¹; H₂ production catalyst & chemical consumption rate¹⁰³; weight factors among economic, social, environmental influence^{104, 105}; pollutant emission ratio during facility installation and CH₄ consumption ratio of SMR process¹⁰⁶; the steam to biomass ratio (S/B) in biomass gasification¹⁰². However, regarding the LCA result, some upstream or downstream parameters may have a much more influence than the foreground parameters related to H₂ production facilities¹⁰⁷. No research could be found that perform a detail and holistic SA and UA regarding all the foreground and background life cycle parameters involved in the H₂ production life cycle according to the best knowledge of the author. Only Yadav et al.¹⁰⁷ perform the SA and UA of parameters involved in upstream solar electricity plant (e.g., PV plant performance ratio, PV plant efficiency, Global horizontal irradiation) in the life cycle CED and GWP analysis to solar-based high-temperature electrolysis system. Besides, rarely of the SA and UA especially regarding the parameters in CCS process can be found in current H₂ production LCA literature.

Chapter 2. LCA methodology and application

2.1 LCA definition

Flourishing since 1970s^{108, 109}, the Life Cycle Assessment methodology aims for assessing potential environmental impacts associated with all life cycle stages (e.g., extraction and processing of raw material, manufacture, distribution and use, recycling or end-of-life treatment) of a commercial product, process, or service^{110, 111}. The 14000 series of environmental management standards of the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), in particular, ISO 14040¹¹² and ISO 14044¹¹³, provide detailed and worldwide accepted procedures for conducting LCA studies. As pointed out by ISO, LCA can fulfil several goals: quantifying material and energy efficiency for a system; identifying improvement opportunities and trade-offs; highlighting hidden or unrecognized issues; promoting a wider communication about how to compare and improve highly complex and difficult to analyse industrial systems.

There are four general phases when conducting a life cycle assessment as shown in Fig. 2.1: Goal and scope definition; Life cycle Inventory analysis; Life cycle impact assessment; Result interpretation. In the goal and scope definition phase, researchers should unambiguously clarify the goal: reasons to perform the study, intended information that is expected to be obtained and the potential audience of the study. The analysis of the scope should state clearly the production system and system boundary, functional unit, reference flow, data quality requirements, assumptions and limitations of the system analysed as well as the allocation procedure used if existing¹¹². In the life cycle inventory analysis stage, a flow diagram, which can be combined with life cycle boundary graphs, can be drawn to clarify the activities in the relevant supply chain to be assessed. To build the life cycle inventories (LCIs), the following steps should be taken: Data collection preparation based on the goal and scope; data collection, allocation, and validation (if needed); relating data to unit process and then the functional unit; and data aggregation¹¹². The Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) stage aims at evaluating the potential environmental and human health impacts due to the life cycle inventories under the defined goal and scope. To complete an LCIA, the impact categories and corresponding characterization models should be selected, followed by classification and characterization of the inventory flows¹¹³. Further operations like normalization, grouping and weighting of the LCIA score can be applied according to the requirement of the goal and scope of the study. And weighting is not recommended by ISO due to its high subjectivity and low comparatives¹¹³. Finally, life cycle interpretation will systematically identify, quantify, check, and evaluate the result from LCIs and LCIA. According to ISO norms¹¹², to understand and determine the confidence level that whether the LCIA result fulfil the goal and scope of the study, following steps should be undertaken in the life cycle result interpretation phase: identification of significant issues based on LCIs and LCIA score; result evaluation considering the completeness, sensitivity and consistency; statement of the conclusions, limitations and recommendations of the study^{112, 113}.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the general phases of a life cycle assessment, as described by ISO 14040

2.2 Goal and scope definition

The goal of this work is to better understand the environmental sustainability of H₂ production technology overcoming the existing limitation as stated in Section 1.2. The research result could serve as basis for governmental officials, policy maker, and companies for the formulation of financing policy aiming to promote renewable and low-carbon H₂ penetration in France. From the angle of the average resource availability and technology market share in France in 2019, this research mainly focuses on the methane reforming (CH₄-to-H₂) pathway and water electrolysis H₂ production fed by renewable electricity (RE-to-H₂).

As stated in Section 1.2, the main tasks of this research were, for all the analysed H₂ production pathways:

- to calculate the potential environmental impacts,
- to locate the main hotspot of each impact categories,
- to analyse the uncertainties and variability in the LCA results by propagating input parameters' uncertainties through the parametric LCA model and assessing the global sensitivity of the results to all these life cycle parameters.

The functional unit of the research, common to all the analysed pathways, is “1 MJ H₂ produced and being compressed to 200 bar”. As indicated in Fig. 2.2 below, the life cycle boundaries of cradle-to-grave assessment include:

For the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway,

- mix of biogas production market in France 2019, unified processes clarified by the ecoinvent 3.6 database, i.e., feedstock collection & transportation, facility construction of the anaerobic digestion (AD) plant (material extraction, transport, and end-of-life treatment), energy & material consumption of AD process, digestate storage applied by each biogas production technologies.
- production mix of natural gas (NG) market in France 2019 (clarified by the ecoinvent 3.6 database), bio-CH₄ upgrading from biogas, and corresponding transportation of CH₄ feedstock to H₂ production site.
- facility construction (material extraction, transport, and end-of-life treatment) of the CH₄ vapor reforming H₂ plant (H₂ compression unit included).
- catalysts, energy & chemical consumption (related transport and end-of-life treatment included) during H₂ production, purification & compression process as well as the corresponding transportation.
- For pathway including the CCS of the flue gas from the H₂ production facility: CCS construction (material extraction, transport, and end-of-life treatment) and energy consumption during CCS process operation.

For water electrolysis H₂ production through solar and wind electricity (solar-to-H₂ and wind-to-H₂ pathway),

- mix of solar electricity production market in France 2019, unified processes clarified by the ecoinvent database, i.e., construction of PV panels and PV power plant network connection & auxiliaries (material extraction, transport, and end-of-life treatment); PV electricity production process, are applied to each solar electricity production technologies.
- mix of wind electricity production market in France 2019, unified processes clarified by the ecoinvent v3.6 database, i.e., construction of wind turbine assembly, wind power plant network connection & auxiliaries (material extraction, transport, and end-of-life treatment); wind electricity production process, are applied to each wind electricity production technologies.
- facility construction (material extraction, transport, and end-of-life treatment) of the water electrolysis unit (H₂ compression unit included).
- water, energy & chemical consumption (related transport and end-of-life treatment included) during water electrolysis H₂ production, purification & compression process.

In the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, co-generated electricity first meets the demand of the H₂ production system. This research accounted for the environment impact of the excess electricity by substitution, where environment impact of average French high voltage electricity is avoided as shown in the attachment.

In RE-to-H₂ pathway, the oxygen produced by the electrolysis unit is vented to the environment without a subsequent utilization, and thus is considered environmental burden free. Except for the RE electricity production phase, the remaining processes in wind-to-H₂ and solar-to-H₂ pathway are identical to each other.

In all three major pathways studied, after purification, the H₂ produced with a purity larger than 99.9% is compressed to the standard H₂ transport pressure nowadays to ensure the comparability to other studies.

Figure 2.2: Flowchart and life cycle boundaries of a) CH₄-to-H₂ b) solar-to-H₂ c) wind-to-H₂ pathway

The feedstock market for each H₂ production pathway (the CH₄ market for CH₄-to-H₂ pathway; solar and wind electricity market to solar-to-H₂ and wind-to-H₂ pathway), presented in Fig. 2.2 within the blue square, is of high complexity under the average resource availability and technology market share in France 2019. Thus, special attention should be paid when defining the life cycle boundaries and corresponding LCI parameters of the feedstock market for each H₂ production pathway to better represent the reality. For the feedstock market in each H₂ production pathway, this research follows the protocol and logic shown in Fig. 2.2, to define the life cycle boundaries, obtain corresponding LCI and parameters' data, thus to build the comparable parametric LCA model best representing the reality.

Figure 2.3: Decision diagram for harmonization of LCA parametric model to feedstock production.

Due to their open-sourced features, compared with other LCA software, Python framework for LCA: Brightway2¹¹⁴ and the algebraic parametrisation BW2 layer: *lca_algebraic* library¹¹⁵ enables a more flexible environment for LCA research, e.g., dynamic LCA research and innovation in LCIA results interpretation, e.g., life cycle model simplifying¹¹⁵ and quick check for impact categories correlation¹¹⁴. To perform a complete and systematic life cycle interpretation, as the internship main task shows above, (detailed analysing of the importance to LCIA results variability regarding each input life cycle parameters' uncertainties and life cycle scenarios; performing the global sensitivity analysis), this research builds the complete LCIs of all the pathway studied together with the data source into parametric LCA model in BW2 based *lca_algebraic* library. The LCA results together with the corresponding result interpretation are then generating by simulating the parametric LCA model built with the *lca_algebraic* library. The parametric LCA model developed in Brightway2¹¹⁴ (BW2) and *lca_algebraic* library¹¹⁵ includes the detailed modeling of the transportation processes for each pathway studied. Besides the transportation process considered by the ecoinvent v3.6 database, all the transportation process to main facilities in the CH₄-to-H₂ and RE-to-H₂ pathways are considered in metric ton*km (t*km thereafter).

2.3 Life cycle inventory

This section gives a detailed description of life cycle inventory for each pathway studied, as well as the data and hypothesis we collected and applied based on the new findings of current H₂ production situation, different data source and existing previous researches. The corresponding Excel spreadsheets and parametric LCA model written in Jupyter notebooks can be found in the supplementary materials attached to this report. The ecoinvent database (version v3.6) 'Allocation, cut-off by classification' is the main source for the background LCIs used in this research.

2.3.1 Methane reforming H₂ production

In the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, the methane in the average French natural gas grid under national level bio-CH₄ gas grid blending is fed into the steam reformer for methane reforming H₂ production. Following the goal and scope of the research, Section 2.3.1.1 describe the LCI of national average methane production mix of France, covering the average resource availability and technology market share of France. Detailed LCI of the methane reforming H₂ production unit, methane reforming H₂ production, H₂ compressor and compression process can be found in Section 2.3.1.2. Section 2.3.1.3 clarify the LCI of carbon capture and storage unit applied to methane reforming H₂ production unit and the corresponding operation process.

2.3.1.1 Methane feedstock production mix in France

Under current French context, methane (mainly exist as NG or biogas) as an important chemical production raw material and energy carriers, is produced by different technologies inland or imported from different NG exporting countries. Regarding biogas, the LCIA results for biogas production will vary based on different types of anaerobic digestion substrate applied as shown in Fig. 2.4. Besides, according to different AD site location, composition of different anaerobic digestion feedstock will change. Together with timely evolving of the technological specificities to AD plant components' production and installation, LCA to French bio-CH₄ production considering average resource availability and technology market share can be complex and embodied with relatively large uncertainty. To represent the national average biogas production mix in mainland France 2019, following the goal and scope definition, this research summarizes the market share of different biogas production technologies in France as follows.

Figure 2.4: Comparison of the normalized LCIA score to 1 m³ biogas produced from different AD technologies and substrate. With LCI taken from ecoinvent v3.6 database¹¹⁶, Lucía et al¹¹⁷, Gourdet et al¹¹⁸.

In the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, we assumed one unit of methane mix shared by fossil NG and bio-CH₄ mix upgraded from biogas mix based on the real situation summarized below and shown in Fig. 2.2 a). The France Biomethane Observatory¹¹⁹, EU biomethane benchmark report¹²⁰, Overview of the biomethane sector in France 2020¹¹⁹ etc., illustrate the current biogas mix (annual production and new installations, financing activity, etc.) in France. The market share of national average methane mix in mainland France 2019 is distinguished between fossil NG supply (average, 99.667%) and bio-CH₄ production (average, 0.333%). Based on the first level territorial units for statistics (LVL1-NTUS)¹²¹, this research divided mainland France into 13 different regions as shown in Fig. 2.5. Due to an almost 100% grid injection rate of all the biogas produced under current French context, one can calculate the specific ratio to the 13 French region from the annual total NG consumption and the biogas production (both in TWh) in each of the 13 French big regions as shown by Equation (1). Using the oracle crystal ball software Ver. 11.1.2, we generate the continuous probability distributions for average bio-CH₄ injection ratio in nation-wide gas grid of France, based $Ratio_{BM}$ calculated from Equation (1).

$$Ratio_{BM} = \frac{BM_{production_{region}}}{NG_{consumption_{national}} \times Population_{region}} = \frac{BM_{production_{region}}}{Capital_{NG} \times Population_{region}} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$Ratio_{BM}$: bio-CH₄ injection ratio in regional NG grid to each of the 13 French big regions.

$BMproduction_{region}$: bio-CH₄ production amount in each of the 13 French big regions, obtained from the renewable gas French panorama 2019, for Île-de-France 209 GWh in 2019¹²².

$NGconsumption_{national}$: average NG consumption in France 2019, which is 3.837E+08GWh¹²³.

$Population_{national}$: French population 2019, which is 67012883 in 2019¹²⁴.

$Capital_{NG}$: French average NG consumption per capital 2019, 5.72606 Gwh/person as calculated.

$Population_{region}$: population in each of the 13 French big region 2019, for Île-de-France 12278210¹²⁵.

Figure 2.5: 13 big regions of France according to first level territorial units for statistics applied¹²¹

According to France Biomethane Observatory, etc., the market share of national average bio-CH₄ production mix in mainland France 2019 is shared by agricultural crop residues AD (average, 75%) and Livestock waste AD (average, 17%) and sewage sludge waste AD (average, 8%). This research applies the amine scrubbing as the upgrading process of biogas into biomethane.

Regarding the French fossil NG supply chain, this research applies the scenario and taken the LCI from the ecoinvent v3.6 database. The LCI of biogas production from agricultural crop residues AD, Livestock waste AD, sewage sludge waste AD is taken from ecoinvent v3.6 database¹¹⁶, Lucia et al¹¹⁷, Gourdet et al¹¹⁸ respectively. For the complexity of the AD biogas production process and the LCI, this research reproduces the LCIA result analysed by the corresponding author to ensure the accuracy and reproductivity of the as research result shown in the supplementary materials. The LCI of biogas amine scrubbing upgrading is taken from Antonini et al.²⁰.

Table 2.5. shows in detail the probability distributions of the bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid, share to each biogas production technology in national average bio-CH₄ production mix as well as the transportation distance of crop residue from the collection field to the AD plant.

2.3.1.2 Methane reforming unit and

For methane reforming unit, this research analyses two type of methane reforming technologies, namely, the steam methane reforming (SMR) and autothermal thermal reforming (ATR). Two water gas shifting (WGS) technologies, namely high temperature (HT) WGS and combined WGS under high and low temperature (HTLT) to both SMR and ATR technologies also falls in this researches' context. The reaction process of the methane reforming and WGS is listed in Equation (2)-(3) below, respectively.

Besides the follow chart shown in Fig. 2.2 a)., with the corresponding model built in Aspen Plus V 8.6, Antonini et al.,²⁰ gives a more systemic description about facility's technical details to the SMR and ATR technologies as well as the HT and HTLT WGS used in this research. The LCI of methane reforming H₂ production, purification, and compression process for all CH₄-to-H₂ pathways analysed is taken from Antonini et al.,²⁰ which is then localized to French context to representing the average resource availability and technology market share of France following the logic of Section 2.3.3.

2.3.1.3 Carbon capture and storage

This research studied the effect of two types CCS technologies, i.e., Methyl diethanolamine recycling (MDEA) CO₂ capture and state-of-art vacuum pressure swing adsorption (VPSA) cycle^{126, 127} on the environmental performance of CH₄-to-H₂ pathway studied. Besides the follow chart shown in Fig. 2.2 a), Antonini et al.,²⁰ gives a detailed technical description to MDEA and VPSA technologies used in this research, based on the corresponding model built in Aspen Plus V 8.6. The LCI of the two CCS technologies is also taken from Antonini et al.,²⁰ and then localized to French context to representing the average resource availability and technology market share of France following the logic of Section 2.3.3. Table 2.5. shows in detail the probability distributions of the energy consumption during CCS operation, and CO₂ transportation distance form the methane reforming H₂ production plant to carbon storage site.

2.3.2 Water electrolysis H₂ with renewable electricity

In the solar-to-H₂ or wind-to-H₂ pathway, electricity generated by the PV panel or the wind farm will fulfil the electricity demand of water electrolysis unit, the H₂ compressor and other auxiliaries included, respectively. Following the goal and scope of the research, Section 2.3.2.1 and 2.3.2.2 describe the LCI of national average solar electricity and wind electricity production mix of France respectively, covering the average resource availability and technology market share of France. Detailed LCI description of the electrolysis unit, electrolysis H₂ production, H₂ compressor and compression process can be found in Section 2.3.2.3.

2.3.2.1 Solar electricity mix in France

●PV plant construction: PV panels market mix in France

The life cycle impact assessment results for PV panels will vary based on different PV panel types as shown in Fig. 2.5. Besides, according to different installation location and application, e.g., ground centralized PV panels or PV panels on façade, slanted or flat roof, the annual solar irradiation available on the PV panels as well as the transportation distance of PV plant components will change. Together with timely evolving of the technological specificities to PV power plant components' production and installation, large uncertainties and difficulties will be induced and encountered while accessing the national average environmental performance of PV electricity production considering the resource availability and technology market share to one country.

To represent the national average solar electricity generation mix in mainland France 2019, following the goal and scope definition, this research summarized different PV panels' market share on national level of France as follows.

Figure 2.6: Comparison of the normalized LCIA score to 1 m² PV panel produced from different technology with LCI in ecoinvent v3.6 database

In solar-to-H₂ pathway, large-scale centralized H₂ production powered by PV panels installed and mounted on the ground were considered by this research. Because centralized captive H₂ production through centralized PV panels on the ground has long been drawing the major interest of French government and companies^{128, 129}. And due to data unavailability, the distributed & semi-centralized H₂ production are not included in the scope of this report. A total area of 100 m² PV plant powered by the nation level's PV panel mix is assumed.

As shown in Fig. 2.2 b), according to the result in IEA's report on Task 12: PV Sustainability Activities¹³⁰, the open ground PV panels market mix in France 2019 is share by 3 types of PV panels: multi-crystal Si PV panel (average, 62.35%), mono-crystal Si PV panel (average, 33.04%), and thin film PV panel (average, 4.83%). The thin film PV panel market of France in 2019, is mainly occupied by Cadmium telluride (CdTe) PV panels and Copper indium gallium selenide (CIGS) PV panels. The share of the two thin film technologies inside the total thin film PV panel market of France in 2019 is 54.77% (CdTe) to 45.23% (CIGS).

The PV panel production market has ushered in huge technological progress and efficiency improvement since 2005, i.e., after the time node in ecoinvent v3.6, as discussed in detail by Besseau¹³¹ and the Methodology Guidelines for PV LCA released by IEA¹³². The latest LCI database for PV panels released by IEA¹³³ are used in this report to overcome the time hysteresis of the ecoinvent v3.6 database following the protocol in Fig. 2.3. Table 2.6. shows in detail the probability distributions of the share to each PV panel type in open ground PV panels market mix for France 2019.

● *PV plant construction: plant network connection unit & auxiliaries*

For the solar-to-H₂ pathway, following the protocol in Fig. 2.3, the network connection unit & auxiliaries apply the same life cycle boundaries and LCIs as defined in the ecoinvent v3.6 database, where the LCI of site preparation process, PV panel installation process, PV mounting system, and the DC/AC inverter, tap water consumption during PV plant installation and operation should be take into consideration.

In the solar-to-H₂ pathway, the inverter used has a rate capacity of 500 kW. The LCI of the DC\AC inverter, the PV panel installation process, and the tap water supplement are directly taken from the ecoinvent v3.6 database. The LCI of the PV mounting system used in this research are derived from IEA's report on Task 12: PV Sustainability Activities¹³⁰, overcoming time hysteresis of ecoinvent v3.6 database. In IEA's report, the mounting system for ground installed PV approves to be very robust. And there is no need to replace them during the whole life span of the PV panels considered in this report. The requirement of site preparation process, including mostly the diesel consumption for land preparation, was recalculated from the data in the ecoinvent v3.6 database to match the installed capacity of the PV model to satisfy the FU. The amount of the PV panel installation process and tap water consumption during PV plant operation was calculated by the same way. The installed capacity of the inverter equals the installed capacity of the PV model. The amount of the PV mounting system, in m², equals to the land area needed for the PV electricity plant, which is 100 m² as assumed. Equation (4) below calculates the installed capacity of the 100 m² PV plant accessed in the solar-to-H₂ pathway.

$$P_{PVplant} = P_{peak} \times area_{PVplant} \times GCR \quad (4)$$

Where,

$P_{PVplant}$: nominal maximum power of the 100 m² PV plant powered by the nation level's PV panel mix, in kW.

P_{peak} : nominal maximum power of the PV panels per m² under Standard Test Condition(STC), 115.06 Wp/m², on average¹³¹.

$area_{PVplant}$: land area for the PV plant, 100 m² assumed.

GCR : ground cover ratio, refers to the area of net PV modules divided by the equivalence ground area of the PV power plant, under specific tilt and azimuth¹³⁴. Besides the land area of the PV panels, there should also be space left for fire prevention and self-shading prevention in the PV plant. GCR is 36% (on average) as calculated by Blondel Paul¹³⁵, under 30° tilt.

● *PV plant construction: related transportation*

In the solar-to-H₂ pathway, IEA's report includes detailed transportation data for each process involved in all kinds of PV panel production's LCI, covering the route from the PV panel production countries to European regional storage. To cover PV panels' transportation from European regional storage to their installation site in mainland France, based on the transportation scenario of Romain Besseau¹³¹, Celik

et al.¹³⁶, and the road information on Goggle map, a two-stage land transportation process was modelled here:

From the production to the installation site, all the components are first transported by train (700 km, average) and then by lorry (300km, average). The two-stage land transportation process was also applied to all the components involved in the PV plant construction and operation, e.g., each component in PV plant network connection unit & auxiliaries (like the PV panel mounting and installation system). Probability distributions for the two-stage land transportation distance are described in Table 2.6.

The mass of each component involved, e.g., PV panels mix, network connection unit & auxiliaries, can be found in their corresponding LCI data source as discussed above. We summarize the information in the corresponding Jupyter Notebooks and Excel spreadsheets in the Supplementary information.

● *PV plant operation: solar irradiance and PV electricity generation in France*

The daily or yearly solar irradiance is the determining factor of the PV electricity generation. The yearly and daily solar irradiance (Wh/m²) for 13 different regions of mainland France for year 2019 are taken from the CAMS radiation service dataset "AGATE" with McClear version 3 and CAMS radiation bias correction¹³⁷. Hereby, the tilt angle was fixed at 30° and azimuth at 180° to represent the maximum annual solar irradiance potential for the PV panels installed in each region of France. The solar irradiance data used in this research can be found in the supplementary materials attached.

With the yearly solar irradiance data for France, we were able to calculate the total electricity production during the whole life cycle of the PV power plant with Equation (5). With Equation (4)-(6) and Equation (9)-(11) below, one can normalize the LCIA result of solar-to-H₂ pathway to one FU base on total H₂ production in facilities' whole lifespan.

$$Elec_{PV} = P_{PVplant} \times \frac{Irradiation}{I_{HTC}} \times PR \times PVLife \times ALR \quad (5)$$

Where,

$Elec_{PV}$: total amount of electricity generated by PV system in total life span of the PV electricity plant, in kWh/yr.

$P_{PVplant}$: nominal maximum power of the 100 m² PV plant powered by the nation level's PV panel mix, in kW, as defined in Equation (4).

$Irradiation$: annual solar irradiance at the location of the PV system under specific tilt and azimuth in kWh/m²/yr. Maximum value among 13 big regions in France 2019¹³⁷ as 1900.59 kWh/m².

I_{HTC} : solar irradiance under STC¹³⁸, which is 1 kW/m².

PR : performance ratio(average, 0.8¹³⁰), indicates the efficiency of the PV system, namely the difference between the actual energy output and the theoretical energy output due to losses occurring the PV electricity generation process, such as thermal and conduction losses¹³⁹.

$PVLife$: lifetime of the PV system in years, 30 years in average¹³².

ALR : Average loss ratio, describes the average efficiency loss of the PV panels during the system's lifetime. Based on the yearly loss ratio¹⁴⁰, it should be calculated with Equation (6).

$$ALR = \frac{1}{PVLife} \sum_{i=1}^{PVLife} \frac{100-Y}{100}^{*(i-1)} = \frac{200-YLR*(PVLife-1)}{200} \quad (6)$$

Where,

YLR : the yearly loss ratio (average, 0.7%¹³²), indicates the efficiency loss of the PV panels during each year in the system's lifetime.

$PVLife$: lifetime of the PV system in years as defined by Equation (5).

Using the oracle crystal ball software Ver. 11.1.2, we generate the continuous probability distributions for $Irradiation$ based on the regional annual solar irradiance data exported from the AGATE database¹³⁷. Logic to set the probability distributions for those parameters involved in Equation (4) - Equation (6) are described in Table 2.6.

2.3.2.2 Wind electricity mix in France

● *Wind plant construction: wind turbine assembly market mix in France*

Fig. 2.7 shows the side-by-side the comparison of wind power LCA between the origin literature results and the corresponding results after harmonized (harmonization of the capacity factor, component lifetime, system boundaries, etc.) by U.S. National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)¹⁴¹. Like for PV solar electricity production, plenty of factors influence one country's wind electricity production,

and thereby induce uncertainty in the LCIA result coming along. According to different technological details, e.g., rotor size, turbine capacity, type and size of the tower, lifetime of each component, there are more than 2000 wind turbine models available and being used in France ¹⁴². The installation location will also influence LCIA results as it determines the available wind resource as well as the transportation distance to each component of the wind farms. Besides, the temporal scale is also important. The technological specificities of the wind power plant might evolve over time. Furtherly, at different time scale, the wind farm installation process will consume the electricity with different grid mix.

Figure 2.7: Comparison of wind LCA results compiled by U.S. NREL between raw results in the original studies and corresponding results after harmonizing (e.g., capacity factor, components' lifetime and system boundaries.)

To represent the national average wind electricity generation mix in mainland France 2019, in the wind-to-H₂ pathway, we assumed one unit of wind farm mix shared by off-shore wind farm and onshore wind farm mix based on the real situation summarized below and shown in Fig. 2.2 b).

The French wind power Observatory ^{143, 144}, Offshore Wind in Europe 2020 ¹⁴⁵ etc., illustrate the current wind electricity market (production, new installations, financing activity, etc.) in France. The market share of national average wind electricity generation mix in mainland France 2019 is distinguished between off-shore wind (average, 0.1%) and onshore wind (average, 99.90%) electricity production. One can calculate the specific ratio from the annual total wind electricity production amount in France and the production amount by type. The annual total wind electricity production in France 2019 was 34.1 TWh from both off-shore and onshore wind power¹⁴⁶. Total off-shore wind electricity production can be calculated by the Equation (9). All the other wind electricity, besides the off-shore wind electricity, are considered coming from the onshore wind turbines.

Wind Power Database (28th July 2021 last version)¹⁴² summarize the technological details for all wind power plant (farm location, turbine model and capacity, hub height, turbine number, etc.) in France. On average, the market share of onshore wind turbine assembly mix is 11.27% (<1MW wind turbine): 82.16% (1-3 MW wind turbine): 6.568% (>3 MW wind turbine). This research considered the off-shore farm in France is all composed by wind turbine assembly with 1-3MW wind turbine, following the currently off-shore wind electricity market in France around 2019¹⁴⁵.

For both onshore and off-shore wind turbine assembly used in the wind farm, this study used their corresponding LCIs from the ecoinvent v3.6 database. For more details for LCI of each wind turbine assembly, e.g., tower and foundation type, please refer to the corresponding Excel spreadsheets and Jupyter Notebook shown in the supplementary material or the ecoinvent v3.6 database. Probability distributions for the market share of wind turbine assembly with different turbine capacity level inside the onshore wind turbine assembly mix covering all the onshore wind farm in France 2019 are described in Table 2.6.

● *Wind plant construction: plant network connection unit & auxiliaries*

In the wind-to-H₂ pathway, the LCIs of network connection unit & auxiliaries corresponding to each wind turbine assembly used in the research are exported from the ecoinvent v3.6 database. We can directly find the amount of the network connection unit & auxiliaries needed for 1 kWh wind electricity production in ecoinvent v3.6 database for each wind farm using different wind turbine assembly. Based on the capacity level of the wind turbine and onshore/off-shore technologies, the types and amount needed for network connection unit & auxiliaries, i.e., the DC\AC transformer, cables, tower, foundation, wind turbine assembly lubricating oil will vary.

With the logic of Equation (8), total amount of wind electricity production for wind farm mix among life span can be calculated. We can then normalize the LCIA impact of the wind-to-H₂ pathway to one FU based on the calculation of Equation (7)-(11) below. The probability distributions for lifetime of network connection unit and corresponding wind turbine assembly are described in Table 2.6.

● *Wind plant construction: related transportation*

Transportation of all the components involved in the wind plant construction and operation, e.g., each component in wind plant network connection unit & auxiliaries and each wind turbine assembly as shown in Table 2.1, from the production site to the installation site are not covered by the ecoinvent 3.6 database.

Following the logic in Fig. 2.3, this research applied the same two-stage land transportation process as defined in Section 2.3.2.1 to the transportation of each component involved in the wind plant construction and operation as shown in Table 2.1, from the production site to the installation site. For off-shore wind turbine, this research considers an oversea transportation of the corresponding component involved in the wind plant construction and operation. The transportation distance of 10 km on average¹³¹.

Table 2.1: Components in the wind plant construction and operation applied with the two-stage transportation process

Component	internal part
Rotor	rotor blades, rotor hub, extender
Nacelle	Nacelle cover, gearbox, generator, shaft, yaw system, flanges, and other
Tower	all kind of steel, epoxy resin and paint
Control electronics	all kind of electronics in the nacelle
Network connection	cables, transformer, sub-station with the circuit breaker and the electricity meter, and others

The mass of each component involved can be found in their corresponding LCI data source as discussed above. We summarized this information in the corresponding Jupyter Notebooks and Excel spreadsheets in the Supplementary information. Probability distributions for the oversea transportation distance of all the component involved in the off-shore wind plant construction and operation are described in Table 2.6.

● *Wind plant operation: wind electricity generation mix in France*

To represent France's actual situation, as discussed above, in the wind-to-H₂ pathway, the research assumed one unit of wind farm mix, which is shared by off-shore wind farm (0.001 unit, on average) and onshore wind farm mix (0.999 unit, on average). One unit of onshore wind farm mix is shared the three different turbine assembly under different turbine capacity level as discussed above (on average, 0.8216 unit of wind farm installed with 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly; 0.1127 unit of wind farm installed with <1 MW wind turbine assembly; 0.0657 unit of wind farm installed with >3 MW wind turbine assembly).

Equation (7) clarifies the installed capacity of one unit wind farm mix representing the national average wind turbine assembly mix in France 2019.

$$P_{Windplant} = Ratio_{offshore} \times P_{1-3MWoffshor} + Ratio_{onshore} \times \sum (Ratio_{turbine,i} \times P_{offshore,i}) \quad (7)$$

Where,

$i =$ '<1 MW wind turbine', '1-3 MW wind turbine', '>3 MW wind turbine'

$P_{Windplant}$: Installed capacity to one unit of wind farm mix representing the national average wind

turbine assembly mix in France 2019, with unit of kW.

$Ratio_{offshore}$: Ratio of wind electricity generated by off-shore wind turbine to all the wind electricity generated in France 2019, 0.1% as calculated.

$P_{1-3MWoffshore}$: Representative capacity of the off-shore wind turbine assembly with turbine capacity level between 1-3 MW 2019 for France, which is 2 MW as defined in ecoinvent 3.6 database.

$Ratio_{onshore}$: Ratio of wind electricity generated by onshore wind turbine to all the wind electricity generated in France 2019, 99.90% as calculated.

$Ratio_{turbine,i}$: Market share of turbine assembly under different turbine capacity level in onshore wind turbine assembly mix for France 2019. For turbine assembly with capacity level of <1MW, 1-3MW, >3MW, on average, the ratio is 11.27%, 82.16%, 6.57%.

$P_{turbine,i}$: Representative capacity for each turbine capacity level defined in ecoinvent 3.6 database. For turbine assembly with capacity level of <1MW, 1-3MW, >3MW, it is 800KW, 2MW, 4.5MW respectively.

$$Production_{wind} = Cf_{turbine} \times P_{Windplant} \times 8760 \quad (8)$$

Where,

$Production_{wind}$: annual electricity production from one off-shore or onshore wind turbine assembly in France 2019 with unit of kWh.

$Cf_{turbine}$: the capacity factor for off-shore or onshore wind turbine assembly, which is the annual net electricity output of the wind turbine divided by the turbines' maximum power capability (net energy output under the turbine's rated power with 8760 hours uninterrupted work each year). 24.50% for onshore wind turbine^{147, 148} and 38% for off-shore wind turbine¹⁴⁹ on average in France in 2019.

$P_{Windplant}$: The total installed capacity of the off-shore or onshore wind turbine in mainland France 2019 in kW summarized by the Wind Power database¹⁴², on average, 0.01 GW of off-shore wind turbine and 16.94GW of onshore wind turbine.

We defined the probability distribution of the capacity factor for both the off-shore, onshore wind turbine in France based on several data sources^{147, 149, 150}. Together with the lifetime of wind turbine, the probability distributions for those parameters in Equation (7) and (8) are described in Table 2.6.

2.3.2.3 Water electrolysis unit

• Water electrolysis unit and electrolysis H_2 production

As shown in Fig. 2.2, this research studied two types of water electrolysis unit: proton exchange membrane electrolyser (PEM) and alkaline electrolyser (AE). In both the PEM and AE unit, balance of plant (BOP) voltage adapting or rectifies the electricity coming from the PV plant or wind plant into proper DC electricity required by the electrolyser stack (the place where the water electrolysis reaction takes place). The stack electrolyzes the deionized water from the French water grid into H_2 and O_2 .

Barei et al.,²⁵ give a detailed technical description of the PEM unit under the present market situation, from where this research taken the LCI of PEM electrolysis unit, both of the BOP and stack. The LCI of the stack to AE unit is taken from the parameterized model developed by Romain Besseau¹³¹. As point out by Barei et al.,²⁵ it can be difficult to give a sound estimation for the LCI of electrolysis unit's BOP. Considering the similarity between the BOP for alkaline and PEM stack¹⁵¹⁻¹⁵³, and due to data limitation, this research consider the same BOP for both the PEM and Ak unit from Barei et al.,²⁵

The efficiency of the electrolyser stack and the global efficiency of the electrolysis unit are determining factors for the H_2 productivity. One can calculate the total H_2 production amount during the entire lifetime for one RE-to- H_2 pathway by Equation (9).

$$H_{2yield_LHV} = H_{2yield_kg} \times LHV_{H2} = \frac{Elec_{gen}}{\frac{Elec_{H2} + Elec_{H2compress}}{\eta_{unit}}} \times LHV_{H2} \quad (9)$$

Where,

H_{2yield_LHV} : the total H_2 production amount during the entire lifetime of the solar-to- H_2 or wind-to- H_2 pathway, in MJ, based on low heating value (LHV).

H_{2yield_kg} : the total H_2 production amount during the entire lifetime of the solar-to- H_2 or wind-to- H_2 pathway, in kg.

LHV_{H2} : the LHV of H_2 in MJ/ kg H_2 , which is 120 MJ/kg and equals to 33.3 kWh/kg¹⁹.

$Elec_{gen}$: total amount of electricity generated by PV plant in solar-to-H₂ or wind plant in wind-to-H₂ pathway in whole lifespan of the facilities, in kWh.

$Elec_{H_2}$: the net electricity demand for water splitting in LHV kWh/ kg H₂, with a 100% efficiency, which is 33.3 kWh/kg H₂ (literally equals to the LHV of 1 kg H₂).

η_{unit} : global efficiency for the electrolysis unit covering all facilities in the system, e.g., stack, electronics, pumps, safety equipment, infrastructure. η_{unit} for the PEM, AE unit (average, 60%) are summarized based on the data from Bareiß et al²⁵, the ecoinvent v3.6 database.

$Elec_{H_2compress}$: the electricity needed by the compressor to compress H₂ for stack outlet pressure (30 bar) to 200 bar, which is 3.91 kWh/kg H₂ as maximum¹⁵⁴.

Equation (10) clarify the calculation of the capacity to the electrolysis unit installed in each RE-to-H₂ pathway.

$$Capacity_{electrolyser} = \frac{\frac{Elec_{H_2}}{\eta_{unit}}}{\frac{Elec_{H_2} + El_{H_2compress}}{\eta_{unit}}} \times P_{REplant} \quad (10)$$

Where,

$Capacity_{electrolyser}$: capacity of the electrolysis unit installed in solar-to-H₂ pathway or wind-to-H₂ pathway.

$Elec_{H_2}$: the net electricity demand for water splitting, as defined in Equation (9).

η_{unit} : global efficiency for the electrolysis unit covering all facilities in the system, as defined in Equation (9).

$Elec_{H_2compress}$: the electricity needed by the compressor to compress H₂ for stack outlet pressure (30 bar) to 200 bar, as defined in Equation (9).

$P_{REplant}$: Installed capacity of the PV plant or the wind farm analysed in solar-to-H₂ pathway or wind-to-H₂ pathway. It equals to $P_{PVplant}$ defined in Equation (4) and $P_{windplant}$ defined in Equation (7) respectively.

The detailed probability distributions for η_{unit} , lifetime for PEMWE and AWE unit and $Elec_{H_2compress}$ in France 2019 are described in Table 2.6.

•H₂ compressor and compression process

To keep consistent with the methane water reforming pathway, we use the most common H₂ compressor type, namely the diaphragm compressor to model the H₂ compression process in the RE-to-H₂ pathway. The LCI per unit diaphragm compressor can be found in the premise database¹⁵⁵. One can calculated the amount of the diaphragm compressor unit needed in RE-to-H₂ pathway with Equation (11).

$$Compressor_{unit} = 1 \times \frac{SysLife}{CompressorLife} = 1 \times \frac{SysLife}{\frac{H_{2unit}}{H_{2yield_{kg}}} \times SysLife} \quad (11)$$

Where,

$compressor_{unit}$: number of compressor unit needed in life time of solar-to-H₂ or wind-to-H₂ pathway.

$SysLife$: life time of solar-to-H₂ or wind-to-H₂ pathway (equals to the lifetime of the PV plant or wind plant respectively).

$CompressorLife$: lifespan of the diaphragm compressor used in RE-to-H₂ pathway.

H_{2unit} : total amount of H₂ can be compressed during the entire lifespan of one compressor, in kg

$H_{2yield_{kg}}$: the total H₂ production amount during the entire life time of solar-to-H₂ or wind-to-H₂ pathway, as defined in Equation (9).

No exact data on the diaphragm compressors' lifetime that in consistent with the diaphragm compressor LCI is found during the research. To better represent the actual situation, we estimate the lifetime of the diaphragm compressor by comparing the H_{2unit} and $H_{2yield_{kg}}$. Thus, the specific durability (in years) of one diaphragm compressor in each RE-to-H₂ pathway can be calculated as shown in Equation (11). The H_{2unit} is calculated as 5906475.3 kg / unit on average as shown in the premise database¹⁵⁵. To consider

the lifetime variation among different facilities, as shown in Table 2.6, this research applied a 15% variance to H_{2un} , according to features of diaphragm compressor¹⁵⁶.

• *Related transportation*

This research applies the two-stage transportation process defined above to all the components involved in the AE and PEM electrolysis unit to the RE-to-H₂ pathway, e.g., the electrolysis stack, BOP, and H₂ compressor, to cover the transportation process from the production site to the installation site.

The mass of each component involved in the AE and PEM electrolysis unit to the RE-to-H₂ pathway, e.g., the electrolysis stack, BOP, and H₂ compressor, can be found from their corresponding LCI data source as discussed above. We summarized this information in the corresponding Jupyter Notebooks and Excel spreadsheets in the Supplementary information.

2.3.3 Regionalization of the LCI to current French context

Localized LCIs data is the basis for studying the environmental performance’s difference for one specific activity among different regions in the world. According to the goal and scope of this research, based on the LCIs cited from all kinds of references as discussed above, the research built the localized LCIs for each H₂ production pathway to reach a better representation of the current French 2019 context. The work is done by solving the problem below following the logic of Fig. 2.8:

Figure 2.8: Decision diagram to build French localized LCIs for each H₂ production pathway

The background or foreground activities inside the LCI for each H₂ production pathway studied by this research should be within the French context, but the original LCI inside the reference literature doesn’t does not predefine the geographic attributes of these LCIs properly. The first case is a complete missing of the geographic attribute information of the LCI. For example, in each RE-to-H₂ pathway, the LCI of PEM water electrolysis unit are taken from Bareiß et al²⁵, which includes Titanium, Aluminum, Copper, etc. However, Bareiß et al²⁵ don’t state which production location or import region of these materials one should choose when we compiling the LCI using the ecoinvent database. The second case is an inappropriate or a too broad geographic attribute resolution used in the original LCI inside the reference literature, which does not adequately represent the French 2019 context. For example, in CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, the LCIs of natural gas (NG) production mix, are taken from Antonini et al’s inventory²². Instead of using the LCI of NG production mix in France, Antonini et al.’s inventory applied the LCI of European average NG production mix. In this second case, the criteria displayed in Table 2.2 were followed to increase the spatial representativity of the LCI. However, not all inventories could be adapted to the French context, given the limited amount of spatially-explicit inventories available in the current ecoinvent database.

Table 2.2: Criteria to choose the localized LCI with proper geographic attributes.

Geographic attributes of the localized LCI to one specific activity can be found in ecoinvent v3.6	Corresponding geographic attributes of the localized LCI to choose in this study
Only France (FR)	FR
FR, some other countries	FR
Switzerland (CH), Europe without Switzerland, some Non-European countries, rest of world (RoW)	Europe without Switzerland
CH, Europe without Switzerland, RoW	Europe without Switzerland
Europe average (RER), RoW	RER
RER, some Non-European countries, RoW	RER
27 European Union country average (EU27), RoW	EU27
Germany (DE), RoW	DE
CH, some Non-European countries, RoW	CH
CH, RoW	CH
Only global average (GLO)	GLO

2.3.4 Scenarios analyzed in each pathway

To summarize, as shown in Fig. 2.9, this research focused on 16 H₂ production pathways in total, which include 12 CH₄-to-H₂ pathways and 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways. The 12 CH₄-to-H₂ pathways vary according to the reformer type (ATR or SMR), the WGSR type (HT water shifting alone or combined LT and HT temperature water shifting), the CCS technologies (no CCS, MDEA CCS, VPSA CCS) and the corresponding carbon capture ratio (90% or 98% carbon dioxide captured). Based on the renewable electricity type (wind electricity or solar electricity), and electrolysis unit type (AE or PEM unit) 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways were analyzed.

Figure 2.9: cases modeled by the research in a) CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, b) RE-to-H₂ pathway

2.4 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

2.4.1 Life cycle impact categories

The choice of the LCIA categories varies among different LCA research on H₂ production, as pointed out by the overview work on H₂ production LCA done by Bhandari et al.,²⁴ and Table. 2.3 below. Based on the highest suggestion from the EU Joint Research Centre (climate change, ozone depletion, respiratory inorganics)¹⁵⁷, the analyses done by other researchers as shown in Table. 2.3 and the specific patterns of the H₂ production pathway studied in this research, the following ‘ILCD 2.0 2018 midpoint’ impact categories in Table. 2.4 were analyzed by this research.

Table 2.3: LCIA categories analyzed for H₂ production LCA study analysed by different authors.

Authors	Year	region	Hydrogen production technologies	LCIA Impact categories
Reiter et al ¹⁰⁰	2015	EU-27	water electrolysis with wind, solar, EU-27 electricity mix; steam reforming of natural gas and crude oil	GWP, CED
Chen et al ¹⁰¹	2019	China	Supercritical water gasification of biomass using concentrated solar energy	GWP, AP, ODP, ADP, EP, POFP
Rajabi et al ¹⁰²	2018	Italy	gasification of almond shell from agro-industrial residue	AP, EP, GWP, POFP, CED

Sarkar et al ¹⁰³	2021	India	acidogenic fermentation (AF) using food waste	all 2002+ midpoint categories except water consumption, water withdrawal, and water turbined
Antonini et al ²⁰	2021	Switzerland	gasification of woody biomass w/o CCS	all ILCD 2.0 2018 midpoint categories
Antonini et al ²²	2020	Switzerland	natural gas and bio-CH ₄ reforming w/o CCS	all ILCD 2.0 2018 midpoint categories
Yadav et al ¹⁰⁷	2020	India	solar-based high temperature water steam electrolysis powered by PV and concentrated solar power	GWP, CED

Table 2.4: LCIA categories analyzed for each H₂ production pathway in this research

LCIA midpoint analyzed	Corresponding ILCD endpoint
Climate change total (GWP)	Climate change
Freshwater and terrestrial acidification (FTA)	Ecosystem quality
Carcinogenic effects (CE)	Human health
Ionizing radiation (IR)	Human health
Ozone layer depletion (OLD)	Human health
Photochemical ozone creation (POC)	Human health
Respiratory effects, inorganics (REI)	Human health
Fossils (FD)	Resources
Land use (LU)	Resources
Minerals and metals (MD)	Resources
Dissipated water (DW)	Resources

2.5 Life cycle result interpretation

2.5.1 Sensitivity and Uncertainty analysis

As indicated in Fig. 2.10, the variance of the parameter value can have a significant impact on LCIA score ^{131, 158}. In LCA study, sensitivity analysis can reveal the robustness of the LCIA result and their sensitivity to uncertainty of life cycle parameters.

As discussed in Section 2.3, this research carefully investigated the foreground and background technologies involved in H₂ production life cycle and their market details to define uncertainty distribution of life cycle parameters influencing the LCA result of each pathway studied. Thus, becoming the first study to perform a detailed and holistic sensitivity (SA) and uncertainty analysis (UA) for H₂ production regarding both the upstream parameters (e.g., the parameters determining marketing of H₂ production feedstock) and the downstream parameters (e.g., parameters determining the CCS process).

The probability distributions (PD) for each identified parameter were defined to represent the current 2019 French H₂ production market following the goal and scope of this research. These parameters were combined in a single parameterized LCA model using the *lca_algebraic* library in Python. The UA and SA for the LCIA score to each impact category among all H₂ production pathway was then performed through Monte Carlo simulation (10,000 iterations).

The parameterized LCA model built in *lca_algebraic* library applies the Sobol indices analysing ¹⁵⁹, namely the variance-based sensitivity analysis¹⁶⁰ as the SA method to the LCIA result obtained. The Sobol indices analysing is a form of global sensitivity analysis that can decompose the variation and uncertainty of model output, and then attribute it to each model input's uncertainty. For one life cycle parameter, the closer its Sobol indices is to 1 (or 100%), the more of the uncertainty to one specific LCIA score is induced by the uncertainty of this life cycle parameter ¹⁶⁰. With the standard deviation (SD) and the arithmetic mean value (μ) calculated through Monte Carlo simulation performed. This research chooses the coefficient of variation (CV), which equals to SD divided by μ , as the indices to reach consistent comparison of LCIA score uncertainty's relative magnitude induced by the life cycle parameters' variation among impact categories with different unit. Section 3.2 discuss the first-order Sobol indices (S1 indices)^{159, 160}, and the LCIA result uncertainty for each H₂ production pathway analysed in detail.

As mentioned in section 2.4, Table 2.5. shows the PD model, PD definition value, and comment for all the parameters involved in the CH₄-to-H₂ pathways. The same content for the wind-to-H₂ and solar-to-H₂ pathways is shown in Table 2.6.

Figure 2.10: Life cycle (a) CO₂ Emissions and (b) cumulative energy demand variation of H₂ supply infrastructures for France, Portugal and USA influenced by uncertainties of life cycle parameters, cited from Alexandre et al ¹⁵⁸.

Table 2.5: PD model and corresponding definition value of parameters in CH₄-to-H₂ pathway

Parameters	Abbreviation	PD model	Comment
average bio-CH ₄ injection ratio in nation-wide gas grid of France	BioCH ₄ _share (%)	PD type: BETA min: 0 max: 7.302 E-01 $\alpha=1.064$; $\beta=1.481$	Four definition value fitted by oracle crystal ball software based on data as discussed in Section 2.3.1.1.
market share of biogas from agricultural crop residues AD in average national bio-CH ₄ production market in France 2019	LSWCH ₄ _share (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 16.3 default: 17 max: 20	Min value taken from Baldino et al. ¹⁶¹ . Default ¹³¹ and max value taken from SIA ^{119, 120}
market share of biogas from sewage sludge waste AD in average national bio-CH ₄ production market in France 2019	SSWCH ₄ _share (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 6 default: 8 max: 11.2	Min and max value taken from ¹⁶¹ . Default taken from ^{22, 120} .
Energy consumption during the operation of MDEA CCS facilities integrated in SMR HTLT WGSR plant with 98% carbon capture efficiency (fossil NG as feedstock).	NG_CCS_elec (kWh/MJ H ₂)	PD type: Triangle min: 5.67 E-03 default: 5.70 E-03 max: 5.73 E-03	Min, default, max taken from Antonini et al. ²² Max are defined as 10% higher energy consumption with lower H ₂ recovery ratio and vice versa for the min value.
Energy consumption during the operation of MDEA CCS facilities integrated in SMR HTLT WGSR plant with 98% carbon capture efficiency (bio-CH ₄ as feedstock).	BM_CCS_elec (kWh/MJ H ₂)	PD type: Triangle min: 5.44 E-03 default: 5.48 E-03 max: 5.52 E-03	Min, default, max taken from Antonini et al. ²² Max is defined as 10% higher energy consumption with lower H ₂ recovery ratio and vice versa for the min value.
Transportation distance of crop residue from the collection field to the AD plant	biowaste_transport_distance (metric ton*km /m ³ biogas produced)	PD type: Triangle min: 9.47 E-03 default: 1.89E-02 max: 2.84E-02	Default is taken from Antonini et al. ²² . Max is defined as 50% higher longer transportation distance and vice versa for the min value.
CO ₂ transportation distance from the methane reforming H ₂ production plant to carbon storage site	CO ₂ _transport_distance (metric ton*km /Kg CO ₂)	PD type: Triangle min: 1.485 E-02 default: 2.97 E-02 max: 4.45 E-02	Default is taken from Antonini et al. ²² . Max is defined as 50% higher longer transportation distance and vice versa for the min value.

Table 2.6: PD model and corresponding definition value of parameters in RE-to-H₂ pathway

Parameters	Abbreviation	PD model	Comment
PV electricity mix			
Annual solar irradiance among the mainland of France	<i>Irradiation</i> (kWh/m ² /yr)	PD type: BETA min: 1.365 E+06 max: 2.401 E+06 $\alpha=1.735$; $\beta=6.822$	Four definition value fitted by oracle crystal ball software based on data taken from the AGATE dataset as stated above.
nominal maximum power of the PV panels per m ²	P_{peak} (Wp/m ²)	PD type: Triangle min: 86.29 default: 115.06 max: 131.49	Calculated based on the nominal maximum power of the 156*156cm ² solar panels. Min value is the value inecoinvent for 2005. Default ¹³¹ and max ¹³¹ stand for the average and innovative technology around 2019 respectively.
performance ratio of the PV panels	<i>PR</i>	PD type: Triangle min: 50 default: 80 max: 90	Estimated base on IEA PV guideline ¹³² , ¹⁶² . 50%-75% represent the value for PV model installed in 1980s. 70%-80% for 1990s. Average value nowadays as 80%-90% for newly installed model.
lifetime of the PV panels	<i>PVLife</i> (yr)	PD type: Triangle min: 20 default: 30 max: 40	30 yr for mature model installed during 1990s until now ¹³² . 40 years for very new model installed ¹³² . 20 years to include the possibility of accident or overuse ¹³²
yearly loss ratio of the PV panels	<i>YLR</i> (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 0.5 default: 0.7 max: 0.9	Min and default as recommended by the IEA PV LCA guideline ¹³² . 0.9% to consider a high degeneration case due to over use ¹⁶³ .
Electricity consumption of Mono Si ingot production (Czochralski-process)	<i>Elec_MonoSi_ingot</i> (kWh/Kg Si ingot)	PD type: Triangle min: 10 default: 32 max: 150	Default as recommended by the IEA PV LCA guideline for average efficiency ¹³² . Min value as the efficiency for new technology ¹³¹ . Max represents the factory using old facilities ¹³¹ .
Electricity consumption of Multi Si ingot production (casted)	<i>Elec_MultiSi_ingot</i> (kWh/Kg Si ingot)	PD type: Triangle min: 7 default: 7 max: 15	Default and min as recommended by the IEA PV LCA guideline ¹³² . Max stands for the modern technology producing Quasi-monocrystalline silicon cell ¹³¹ .
ground coverage ratio of the PV plant	<i>GCR</i> (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 36 default: 36 max: 45	36% stands for the average value ¹³⁵ to 30° tilt maintaining the minimum acceptable shading angle as 20°. Max value ¹³⁵ consider the variance of PV panels tilt angle, PV system's Fire prevention pathway area, and the self-shading prevention area.
Market share of monocrystalline silicon panels in France PV panels market	<i>Ratio_monoSi</i> (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 30.1 default: 33.04 max: 49	Market share of monocrystalline silicon panels keep increasing. Min stands for the situation in 2017 ¹⁶⁴ . Default as calculated by the IEA PV LCA guideline for 2019 ¹³² . 49% stand for the region which has a higher share up to the world average ¹⁶⁵ .
Market share of thin film panels in France PV panels market	<i>Ratio_thinfil</i> (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 4.83 default: 4.83 max: 10	Default and min as calculated by the IEA PV LCA guideline for 2019 ¹³² . 10% stand for the region which has a higher share up to the world average ¹⁶⁴
Wind electricity mix			
Installed capacity of the working off-shore wind turbine in France 2019	<i>CapacityOffshore</i> (GW)	PD type: Linear min: 0.01 default: 0.01 max: 0.48	Installation speed of off-shore turbine keeps slow before 2019 but keep increasing. Min and default represent the average situation in France 2019 ¹⁴² . Max value talking into the influence of off-

Capacity factor of the working off-shore wind turbine in France 2019	$C_{f_{offshore}}$ (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 33 default: 38 max: 55	shore wind plant under construction ¹⁴² . Default stand for the average for all off-shore wind turbine in Europe ¹⁴⁹ . Max stands for the monthly highest value or all European off-shore wind turbine ¹⁴⁹ . Min stands for the lowest capacity factor in summer for all European off-shore wind turbine ¹⁵⁰ .
Capacity factor of the working onshore wind turbine in France 2019	$C_{f_{onshore}}$ (%)	PD type: Normal default: 25 Std: 0.01	Two definition value fitted by oracle crystal ball software based on capacity factor of onshore wind turbine in each of the 13 big regions in France taken from the Statista dataset ¹⁴⁷ and the corresponding land area of each region ¹²¹ .
Wind turbine life time	Turbine_life (yr)	PD type: Triangle min: 15 default: 20 max: 25	Default stand for the average ¹³¹ . Min stand for the situation where turbine is often overload with long working time annually ¹³¹ . Max stand for the situation under good maintenance ¹³¹ .
Network connection unit & auxiliaries			
PV inverter lifetime	Inverter_life (yr)	PD type: Triangle min: 10 default: 15 max: 30	Default stand for the average ¹³² . Min stand for the situation where inverter is often overload with long working time annually ¹³² . Max stand for the situation under good maintenance ¹³² .
PV inverter specific weight	Inverter_spec_weight (kg/KVA)	PD type: Triangle min: 1 default: 2 max: 4	Default stand for the average under average technologies nowadays ¹³¹ . Min stand for the old technology, which is the value record inecoinvent database. Max stand for the very new innovative technology nowadays ¹³¹ .
Life of network connection unit & auxiliaries for wind plant	Wind_network_life (yr)	PD type: Triangle min: 15 default: 20 max: 25	Default stand for the average ¹³¹ . Min stand for the situation where facilities are often overload with long working time annually ¹³¹ . Max stand for the situation under good maintenance ¹³¹ .
Water electrolysis unit			
global efficiency for the electrolysis unit (both PEM and AWE unit)	Effi_electrolysis (%)	PD type: Triangle min: 50 default: 60 max: 70	With the identical BOP for both the AE and PEM unit. The stack efficiency for the PEM and AWE unit is identical base on reference ^{25, 166} . Default stand for the average ^{25, 166} . The mix and max estimated base on the reference literature.
Lifetime of stack in PEM unit	PEM_stack_life (h)	PD type: Triangle min: 40000 default: 50000 max: 60000	Default stand for the average ²⁵ . Min stand for the situation where facilities are often overload ²⁵ . Max stand for the situation under good maintenance ²⁵ .
Lifetime of balance of plant (BOP) in PEM and AE unit	BOP_life (yr)	PD type: Triangle min: 18 default: 20 max: 22	Default stand for the average ²⁵ . Min stand for the situation where facilities are often overload with long working time annually ²⁵ . Max stand for the situation under good maintenance ²⁵ .
Lifetime of AE stack	AWE_life (h)	PD type: Triangle min: 60000 default: 75000 max: 90000	Default stand for the average ¹⁶⁷ . Min stand for the situation where facilities are often overload with long working time annually ¹⁶⁷ . Max stand for the situation under good maintenance ¹⁶⁷ .

Total amount of H ₂ can be compressed during the entire lifespan of one compressor	H_{2un} (kg/unit)	PD type: Triangle min: 5.021 E+06 default: 5.906 E+06 max: 6.792 E+06	As stated above, a 15% variance base to the average value is applied base on the variance of the H ₂ compressor lifetime ¹⁵⁵ . Min stand for the situation where facilities are often overload with long working time annually. Max stand for the situation under good maintenance.
Electricity needed to compress 1 kg H ₂ by the H ₂ compressor	Elec_H ₂ _compress (Kwh/Kg)	PD type: Triangle min: 2.7 default: 3.91 max: 3.91	Default and max stand for the isentropic H ₂ compression, based on the T-S diagram of H ₂ ¹⁵⁴ . Min value is the energy consumption of the modern high efficiency compressor ¹⁶⁸ .
Transportation			
Distance for lorry transport in the two-stage transportation model	Transport_lorry	PD type: Triangle min: 40 default: 700 max: 1400	Generated based on the transportation scenario of Romain Besseau ¹³¹ , Celik et al ¹³⁶ ., and the road information on Goggle map. Default represents the average value from the storage site to the installation site. Min and max value stand for the extreme cases of short and long distance transport.
Distance for transport by train in the two-stage transportation model	Transport_train	PD type: Triangle min: 0 default: 300 max: 600	Generated based on the transportation scenario of Romain Besseau, Celik et al., and the road information on Goggle map. Default represents the average value from the storage site to the installation site. Min and max value stand for the extreme cases of short and long distance transport.
transportation distance for off-shore wind turbine component on the ocean	Transport_ocean_wind	PD type: Triangle min: 0 default: 10 max: 100	Default represents the average value from the shore to the installation site ¹³¹ . Min and max value ¹³¹ stand for the extreme cases of long and short distance transport.

Chapter 3. Results and discussion

3.1 LCIA result discussion

3.1.1 Methane reforming H₂ production

3.1.1.1 unit process contribution LCIA result

By simulating the parametric LCA model built in python based *lca_algebraic* library, this research analysed the unit process contribution to the LCIA result for 12 CH₄-to-H₂ pathways, as shown in Fig.3.1-Fig.3.2. LCIA score in Fig.3.1-Fig.3.2 stands for the arithmetic mean obtained through Monte Carlo simulation. Each bar in Fig. 3.1 - Fig.3.2 contain the box plot of uncertainty distribution to each impact categories. For some of the impact categories, i.e., GWP, POC, the uncertainty calculated from parametric LCA model is relatively low. Thus, only P10 and P95 of the LCIA result is plotted for these impact categories. Fig. 3.1 to Fig.3.2 only show impact categories whose unit process contribution patterns is representative to all impact categories considered. Supplementary materials contain the details and corresponding graph of the unit process contributions of all LCIA categories studied.

● *Global warming potential (GWP)*

For climate change, if not applying CCS technology, under the average bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid, for both the SMR and ATR pathway, GWP of H₂ production can reach up to 0.089 kg CO₂/MJ H₂. Direct CO₂ emissions from the reformer flue gas will contribute up to 85% of the total.

However, if a CCS system is used, its clearly that the higher the carbon capture ratio is, the lower the GWP score. Among the pathway studied, the performance difference between VPSA and MDEA CCS technologies is very small. VPSA technology can reduce the global warming potential slightly more compared with the MDEA CCS pathway.

The H₂ production efficiency gradually increases when moving from HT SMR (case 1 - 4) to HTLT SMR (case 5 - 8) and then to HTLT ATR (case 9 - 12). Thus, reducing the GWP per MJ of H₂ produced under the same CCS technology. For climate change, ATR HTLT VPSA CCS (case 12), comes with the lowest GWP, namely 0.018 kg CO₂/MJ H₂.

Next to the direct CO₂ emissions from the reformer flue gas, the fossil NG supply chain is another important contributor to the GWP of methane reforming H₂ production. Contribution of GWP from fossil NG supply chain vary between 1.35 E-02 to 1.38 E-02 CO₂/MJ H₂ among all the 12 pathways studied. For pathways with high carbon capture ratio, its contribution can cover 66%-78% (case 11-12) of the total score. This high contribution is due the structure of current French national NG market: 27% of the NG consumed in France 2019 is namely imported from Russia (RU) ¹¹⁶. The long NG transportation distance from Russia to France requires the construction of long-distance pipeline and massive NG combustion for corresponding high pressure NG transportation process, which explains its high climate change impact¹¹⁶.

● *Photochemical ozone creation (POC), ozone layer depletion (OLD), fossil resources depletion (FD)*

LCIA score variation for POC, OLD, and FD among 12 pathways studied is very different to the variation of GWP among pathways. Including CCS facility in the context of system boundaries will worsen the environmental performance of these indicators. This is not only because of the construction process of the CCS facilities and pipelines and the corresponding material production, but rather related to the electricity consumption during the CCS operation. Including CCS will lead to 1%-1.5%, 1%-1.2%, 2.4%-3.7% increase for POC, OLD and FD score respectively. Due to a relatively higher energy consumption, compared with MDEA CCS technology, VPSA CCS technology will increasing the score of POC, OLD and FD by 1.3%-2.3%, 1.1%-1.8%, 1.7-3.7%, respectively. For these three impact categories, the NG supply chain is the biggest contributor to the final LCIA score, with more than 60%,95%, 88% of the total score of POC, OLD and FD respectively. For OLD and FD, NG transportation from RU is again the main contributor inside the fossil NG supply chain, due to the long transportation distance. For POC, besides the NG transportation from RU to FR, the NG sweetening process during the Russian NG production is equally important. And for POC, another obvious contributor are the direct emissions from the reformer furnace. Due to technical difference, the ATR

technology will emit more NO_x, thus increasing the POC result by around 42% compared with SMR. Among all the pathways studied, case 12 shows the highest result of POC, OLD, and FD, namely 8.0E-05 kg NMVOC/MJ H₂, 1.53 E-08 kg CFC-11/MJ H₂, and 1.51 MJ/MJ H₂, respectively. And case 1 the lowest, which is 5.47 E-05 kg NMVOC/MJ H₂, 1.43 E-08 kg CFC-11/MJ H₂, 1.31 MJ/MJ H₂.

● *Respiratory effects (REI), freshwater and terrestrial acidification (FTA)*

With the same reason as stated in the interpretation of POC, OLD, and FD result, including CCS facility into system boundary will worsen the environmental performance for REI and FTA. Among all 12 pathways, more than 57% and 47% of the total score of REI and FTA comes from fossil NG supply chain. Russian NG production and transportation process is still the most important contributor inside the fossil NG supply chain, which is followed by the Norwegian NG production and corresponding transportation process. Besides, NG reforming facilities construction process together with the corresponding material extraction (plant infrastructure) ranked as the third critical hotspot, which contribute 15%-20% and 9%-12% to the total score of REI and FTA, respectively. And contribution from catalyst & absorbent production and transportation is comparable to the contribution of plant infrastructure in total score of FTA. Nickel production and transportation contribute around 44% and 76% to the total contribution of catalyst & absorbent for REI and FTA respectively. Pathways applying the ATR NG reforming process will lead to an increase of the REI and FTA score due to larger NO_x emission from the reformer furnace, which will increase the score of REI and FTA 14-20% and 24%-27.8% compared with the corresponding SMR reforming process, respectively. Among all the pathway studied, highest result of REI and FTA goes to case 12, which is 3.15 E-10 disease i./MJ H₂, 8.94 E-05 mole H⁺_{eq}/MJ H₂, respectively. And lowest goes to case 1, which is 2.36E-10 disease i./MJ H₂, 6.75 E-05 mole H⁺_{eq}/MJ H₂.

● *Dissipated water (DW), ionizing radiation (IR)*

For DW and IR, variation of electricity consumption during the CCS operation process has a very significant impact on the final LCIA score. A higher carbon capture ratio requires a higher electricity consumption. And, under national average resource availability and technology mix for France, nuclear electricity contributes around 70% of the electricity available on the grid. Pressurized water reactor (PWR) generates almost all the nuclear electricity in France, which will consume massive amount of water (2.84 kg water/kWh nuclear electricity as indicated in ecoinvent v3.6 database¹¹⁶) and generating large pile of radioactive waste during the PWR unit operation. The second largest electricity source in France, hydro-electricity, also has a large water footprint: up to 810 kg water/kWh electricity¹¹⁶. Pathways without CCS can co-generate electricity necessary to cover the demand of the SMR NG reforming H₂ production facilities' operation, so that very little electricity is required from the grid.

Thus, including MDEA CCS facility in the system boundaries of SMR NG reforming pathways will lead to 43.28 % - 61.31 % and 640.10 % - 890.43 % increase of the DW and IR results compared with the pathway without CCS technology. For pathway applying ATR NG reforming, electricity consumption during ATR NG reforming facilities' operation is already very high compared to operation of SMR NG reforming H₂ production facilities. So that including MDEA CCS facility into ATR NG reforming pathway will increase the DW and IR score to a lower extend, namely 29.32% - 33.80% and 74.49%-85.91% respectively, compared with the corresponding pathway without CCS. Furthermore, due to a relatively higher electricity consumption during operation, including VPSA CCS technology into the system boundaries, will lead to 8.08% - 22.53% and 18.47% - 73.13% increasing to DW and IR score respectively, compared with the corresponding value of pathway with MDEA CCS facility.

For DW, another important contributor is the Norwegian fossil NG production and transportation process, which will contribute more than 10% to the final LCIA score among the 12 cases studied. This is mainly due to the drying process of Norwegian fossil NG, which consumes lot of electricity from Norway electricity grid. And 93.4% of the electricity on Norwegian electricity grid is hydroelectricity as indicated by the ecoinvent v3.6 database¹¹⁶. Among all the pathway studied, highest result of DW and IR goes to case 12, which is 3.295 E-03 m³ water/MJ H₂, 7.92 E-03 kg U_{235-eq}/MJ H₂, respectively. And lowest goes to case 1, which is 1.167 E-03 m³ water /MJ H₂, -3.07 E-04 kg U_{235-eq}/MJ H₂.

● *Land use (LU), carcinogenic effect (CE), minerals and metals depletion (MD)*

Unlike all the impact categories discussed above, for LU, CE, and MD, NG reforming facilities construction process together with the corresponding material extraction and transportation (plant infrastructure) becomes the most critical contributor of the LCIA score among the 12 pathways analysed. For LU, the production, or growing, of sawnwood, which is a major construction material of the NG

reforming facilities used in France, is very land consuming. Thus, the sawnwood consumption is the main contributor within the plant infrastructure. The fossil NG supply chain ranks as the second most important contributor to the LU score of all the pathway analyzed. This is mainly due to the related NG transportation process, where a lot of sand is consumed for the pipeline network construction. Inside the contribution from electricity from/to the grid, the main contributor is the wood chips production, where a lot of wood chips is consumed for electricity and heat co-generation nationwide in France.

For MD, the plant infrastructure contributes more than 79% of the total LCIA score among all the 12 pathways analyzed. This is mainly because the NG reforming facilities construction is brazing solder intensive in France. And the main hotspot inside the plant infrastructure falls to the cadmium free brazing solder production, while a lot of zinc is consumed during the production process.

For CE, the plant infrastructure is as important to the fossil NG supply chain. Inside the plant infrastructure, the main hotspot is the chromium steel and low-alloyed steel production, or more accurately, is the mostly widely used steel production technology in France: converter steel production technology. Regarding the fossil NG supply chain, production, and transportation of NG from Russia (especially the long transportation distance) contributes equally with the production and transportation of NG from Norway (especially the off-shore NG production process). Among all the pathways studied, the highest results of LU, CE, and MD occur for case 12, which is $5.19 \text{ E-02 kg Soil Organic/MJ H}_2$, $2.06 \text{ E-10 CTUh/MJ H}_2$, $2.28 \text{ E-07 kg Sb}_{\text{-eq}}/\text{MJ H}_2$, respectively. And the lowest for case 1, which is $3.63 \text{ E-02 kg Soil Organic/MJ H}_2$, $1.90 \text{ E-10 CTUh/MJ H}_2$, $2.21 \text{ E-07 kg Sb}_{\text{-eq}}/\text{MJ}$, respectively.

● *special focus: contribution from biomethane supply chain*

Currently the bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid is very small, which is 0.33% for French national average as discussed in Section 2.3.1. However, for the REI, DW, LU scores to all 12 pathways analysed, the contribution from the bio-CH₄ supply chain varies from 5.2% - 23.7%, which is quite high compared with the minor bio-CH₄ penetration in French NG market. For DW, this is mainly due to the bio-CH₄ upgrading process, more exactly, the production of the bio-CH₄ upgrading catalyst: 2 wt % potassium iodide solution, which is quite a water consuming process as indicated by the ecoinvent v3.6 database ¹¹⁶. For LU, the key contributor inside the bio-CH₄ supply chain is the construction of the anaerobic digestion plant and the bio-methane upgrading plant, during which a lot of laminated timber is consumed. Growing the softwood for laminated timber production is also land consuming. For REI, the livestock waste biogas production process is the main contributor to the bio-CH₄ supply chain, or more precisely, the ammonia emitted from the storage process of the AD substrate and digestate produced.

Figure 3.1: Unit process contribution LCIA result to 12 CH_4 -to- H_2 pathways made with uncertainty for a) Climate change total, b) Photochemical ozone creation, c) Freshwater and terrestrial acidification, d) Land use. Case from 1 to 12 corresponds to the case ranked in Figure 2.9.

Figure 3.2: Unit process contribution LCIA result to 12 CH₄-to-H₂ pathways make with uncertainty for Dissipated water. Case from 1 to 12 corresponds to the case ranked in Figure 2.9 a).

3.1.1.2 Scenario variation and further comparison

• Comparison with other researches

From the angle of comprehensive trade-off to all impact categories studied, the LCIA scores of the pathway with least environmental impacts among the HT SMR pathway (case 1 - 4), HTLT SMR pathway (case 5 - 8), and HTLT ATR pathway (case 9 - 12) are shown in Fig. 3.3. Supplementary material includes the detailed comparison of the LCIA score of each pathway of the HT SMR pathway, HTLT SMR pathway, and HTLT ATR pathway.

Figure 3.3: optimal pathway with least environmental influence among the HT SMR pathways, HTLT SMR pathways, and HTLT ATR pathways.

As shown in Fig.3.3, among all the 12 pathways studied, applying the VPSA CCS with 98% carbon capture ratio to ATR NG reforming facilities leads to the lowest GWP per MJ H₂ produced. However, the construction of CCS facilities together with the corresponding building material (e.g., compressor and pipeline to CO₂ storage site) production, as well as the electricity consumption during CCS operation contribute significantly to other environmental impacts, as explained in Section 3.1.1.1. And

the higher the carbon capture ratio, the higher the score to other impact categories, as shown in Fig.3.1-3.2. With a comprehensive trade-off to all impact categories, case 7, namely the SMR HTLT H₂ production with MDEA CCS and 98% carbon capture ratio, is taken as the optimal pathway among the 12 pathways studied. Case 7 is further compared with the H₂ production in CH context under the same technical details (namely the SMR HTLT H₂ production with MDEA CCS and 98% carbon capture ratio) studied by Antonini et al.,²² as shown in fig. 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Comparison of unit process contribution LCIA result between this research and result from Antonini et al.²²

In Fig. 3.4, all bars labelled with number 1 present the results from Antonini et al.,²² which is LCIA result for SMR HTLT H₂ production adopting the fuel supply chain with 5%:95% bio-CH₄ to fossil NG ratio, to compare results under the most consistent life cycle boundaries. All bars labelled with number

2 represent the unit process contribution LCIA result of case 7 in this research under French national average bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid 2019 (indicated in Table 2.5 above). Finally, all bars labelled with number 3 represent the corresponding LCIA result of case 7 in this research under highest bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid 2019 (indicated in Table 2.5 above).

Differences between the NG supply chain in FR and European-average context induce interesting variation between this research's result and the result of Antonini et al.²² The fossil NG supply chain in FR used in the 12 pathways studied, imports 27% NG from Russia¹¹⁶. While importing NG from Russia to France is quite polluting in terms of NG sweetening and transportation as discussed above in Section 3.1.1.1., the NG transportation distance in European-average fossil NG supply chain¹¹⁶ applied by Antonini et al.²² is much shorter, which embodied with lower pollutant emission, i.e., CO₂ and CFCs. Thus, compared with the result of Antonini et al, a larger contribution from the fossil NG supply chain to the total LCIA score calculated by this research can be observed in terms of GWP, OLD, POC and MD.

For the European-average fossil NG supply chain applied by Antonini et al, 14.6% of the fossil NG is supplied from Great Britain (GB). The off-shore NG exploitation (major NG production technologies in GB) generates massive amount of low-level radioactive waste, thus, endowing the European-average fossil NG supply chain with higher IR score compared with the NG supply chain in the FR context.

The second interesting process which makes a difference between the result of this research and Antonini et al²² is the source of electricity consumed during H₂ production, purification, compression and the CCS facilities operation. Antonini et al.,²² use electricity from the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E). On the contrary, as discussed in Section 3.1.1.1, the majority of the electricity in France is produced from nuclear power plant. And despite the massive radiative waste generated during nuclear electricity production, the nuclear electricity's LCIA score to GWP, POC, REI, LU is much less than the score of the electricity from ENTSO-E¹¹⁶.

Regarding the bio-CH₄ supply chain, Antonini et al.²² as assume it as environmentally burden free, which means that they allocate the environmental influence of the anaerobic digestion process to the food and agricultural sector²². Thus, the direct comparison of our results for the bio-CH₄ supply chain and the ones from Antonini cannot be performed. After Ecoinvent database is updated from version 3.5 to version 3.6, methane steam reforming facilities construction (plant infrastructure) becomes brazing solder intensive in France, where a lot of zinc is consumed during the production process. Antonini et al.'s result is base on Ecoinvent v3.5 database, thus, the direct comparison of the methane steam reforming plant infrastructure in our result with the ones from Antonini cannot be performed.

● *Further scenario variation*

Figure 3.5: LCIA score for SMR HTLT MDEA CCS 98% pathway regarding different electricity source and corresponding comparison with wood gasification technology

Further analysing to the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway regarding the source of electricity consumed during H₂ production, purification, compression, and the CCS facilities operation is shown in Fig. 3.5. Fig. 3.5 also shown the LCIA score of dry wood gasification H₂ production through three different gasification pathway taken from Antonini et al.,²⁰ : the heat pipe reformer (HPR) and entrained flow gasifier (EF). Still, in Fig. 3.5, analysing the influence of different electricity source is based on case 7. When replacing the electricity source from French electricity grid to electricity from ENTSO-E, Norwegian and Danish electricity grid (94.1% Norwegian electricity generated by hydro power and 48% Danish electricity comes from wind¹¹⁶), IR score will greatly reduce since there is large nuclear electricity share in FR electricity grid as discussed above. And IR score for case using Norwegian electricity is slightly lower than case with Danish electricity. Case 7 using Norwegian electricity has a much higher DW score than other cases shown in Fig. 3.5 b), because of the large water footprint of hydroelectricity as discussed above. However, regarding GWP, FTA, CE, H₂ production using Norwegian electricity will generate the least score for the three impact categories, which is followed by H₂ production using FR electricity, and the wind electricity. H₂ production using Norwegian electricity will also induced smallest LCIA score for OLD, POC, REI, FD, LU. Difference among OLD, POC, REI, FD score induced by H₂ production is minor when using electricity from other source exclude Norwegian electricity. When using Danish electricity in H₂ production, large amount of LU will be induced in the final LCA result. This is because the importance of biomass electricity in Danish electricity grid, where the biomass cultivation process will occupy large land area.

However, when comparing with the wood gasification H₂ production process, influence of the electricity source variation to the final LCA result of methane reforming H₂ production is very minor as shown in Fig. 3.5 a). Only the score of IR will gain a visible decrease when replacing the FR electricity with electricity from other source analysed in Fig. 3.5 a). This is understandable since all the impact categories except IR is not sensitive to the electricity consumption ratio during the operation of H₂ production and the CCS facilities, as described in Section 3.2.1 below. Besides, the score of DW will gain a visible increase when replacing the FR electricity with electricity from Norwegian electricity grid. Antonini's research indicate that oxyEF wood gasification pathway is embodied with lower environmental impact compared with HPR pathway. Comparing with methane reforming H₂ production pathway under average French resource availability and technology mix, namely the case 7, both the two wood gasification H₂ production pathway has an extremely lower GWP. Actually, the case 12, whose GWP is the lowest among all the 12 pathway analysed by this research, is just comparable to the HPR wood gasification pathway without CCS studied by Antonini et al.,²⁰ in terms of GWP. Besides, in terms of FTA, IR, POC, REI, DW case 7 is comparable to the corresponding score to oxyEF wood gasification with CCS. And CE of case 7 is comparable to the corresponding score to HPR wood gasification with CCS. For MD, FD, and OLD, score of case 7 is relatively higher than both wood gasification pathway shown in Fig. 3.5. a).

3.1.2 Water electrolysis H₂ with renewable electricity

3.1.2.1 unit process contribution LCIA result

Similar to CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, this research analysed the unit process contribution to the LCIA result for 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways, as shown in Fig.3.6. LCIA score in Fig.3.6 stands for the arithmetic mean obtained through Monte Carlo simulation. Each bar in Fig.3.6 contain the box plot of uncertainty distribution to each impact categories. Supplementary materials contain the details and corresponding graph of the unit process contributions of all LCIA categories studied.

● *Global warming potential (GWP), Photochemical ozone creation (POC)*

The production, transportation, and construction of electrolysis unit plant infrastructure, e.g., the electrolyser BOP, H₂ compressor is the most important contributor to the LCIA score of GWP and POC for both the wind-to-H₂ pathway and solar-to-H₂ pathway, which contribute 58.9%-70.5%, 53.5%-62.9% for GWP and POC respectively. This high contribution can be furtherly attributed to the massive concrete consumption during the construction of electrolysis unit foundation. This research chooses the 40MPa (compressive strength) concrete, in which the production process of clinker (basic raw material for concrete production) is very CO₂ and NO_x emission intensive under the current French national context¹¹⁶. The remaining LCIA score of GWP and POC in solar-to-H₂ pathway and wind-to-H₂ pathway mainly contributed by the French national average solar and wind electricity production process. Under French national average resource availability and technologies market mix, most of the

multi-Si and mono-Si PV panels is produced and imported from China¹³³, and these processes are CO₂ and NO_x emission intensive due to current fossil energy based Chinese energy structure. The production of PV panel mounting system, contribute equally to GWP and POC in solar-to-H₂ pathway compared with the Si PV panels production and transportation process due to the production of aluminium wrought alloy used in PV panel mounting system. Under current European-average context, aluminium wrought alloy production is very electricity intensive, thus is CO₂ and NO_x emission intensive¹¹⁶.

For wind electricity supply chain, contribution of GWP and POC mainly comes from the construction process of 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly, since most of the onshore wind electricity is generated by 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly under current French context. This high contribution comes from the massive low-alloyed steel used in the construction of 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly. The low-alloyed steel production process in France is CO₂ and pollutant emission intensive as described above in section 3.1.1.1. Besides, under French average resource availability and technology market mix, majority of the wind turbine farm is located at remote area with low population. To get access to the wind powerplant site, specific road should be built. The road construction process is another important contributor to GWP and POC score following the low-alloyed steel production process. Due to the large amount of diesel and petroleum consumption for road construction as well as the road construction material transportation process, the road construction process is CO₂ and other pollutant emission intensive. Among all the pathways studied, case 1 shows the highest result of GWP and case 2 shows the highest result of POC, namely 5.46E-02 kg CO_{2-eq}/MJ H₂, 1.53 E-08 kg NMVOC/MJ H₂, respectively. Case 3 shows the lowest result of GWP and POC, namely 2.62E-02 kg CO_{2-eq}/MJ H₂, 1.03 E-04 kg NMVOC/MJ H₂, respectively.

Figure 3.6: Unit process contribution LCIA result to 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways make with uncertainty. Case from 1 to 4 corresponds to the case ranked in Figure 2.9 b).

● *Freshwater and terrestrial acidification (FTA), Ionizing radiation (IR), Fossil resources depletion (FD), Respiratory effects (REI)*

For FTA, IR, FD and REI, French national average solar electricity supply chain and electrolysis unit plant infrastructure is the major contributor to the LCIA score of solar-to-H₂ pathway (case1-case2) and wind-to-H₂ pathway group (case3-case4), respectively. They contribute more than 44.95%-56.88%, 36.81%-56.95% of the LCIA score to these impact categories in solar-to-H₂ pathway and wind-to-H₂ pathway. The half remaining LCIA score of FTA, IR, FD, and REI in solar-to-H₂ pathway and wind-to-H₂ pathway are mainly contributed by electrolysis unit plant infrastructure and French national average solar electricity supply chain, respectively. For FTA, contribution from the production, transportation and EoL of AE electrolysis stack contribute equally compared with French national average wind electricity supply chain in wind-to-H₂ pathway, and is half of the contribution from French national average solar electricity supply chain in solar-to-H₂ pathway.

With similar reason discussed in GWP, the production of aluminium wrought alloy used in PV panel mounting system, Chinese multi-Si and mono-Si PV panels production and transportation process contribute equally to the higher LCIA score of the French solar electricity supply chain. For plant infrastructure, again, like GWP, the main contributor of the high LCIA score of electrolysis unit plant infrastructure to FIA, FD, REI mainly come from the production process of clinker (basic raw material for concrete production), where the hard coal burned in clinker production, diesel burning in the production process of cement and clinker, as well as the cement transportation process contribute equally. Besides the reason explained in GWP, the production of electricity consumed by cement production process under French context is endowing with huge IR footprint as discussed in Section 3.1.1.1, which is the main contributor to the high LCIA score of electrolysis unit plant infrastructure to IR.

Regarding the average French wind electricity supply chain in wind-to-H₂ pathway, the production process of copper (basic component for 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly), is the main contributor for the high FTA score. Under current French context, major technology for copper is flash smelting furnaces reducing and refining, which is sulphur dioxide emission intensive. The main contributor for the high IR score of the can be further attributed to the production of average French electricity consumed during the wind turbine assembling, mounting and end-of-life (EoL) removal of the turbine as explained above. The main contributor for the high LCIA score of FD and REI mainly comes from the massive low-alloyed steel used in the construction of 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly, with the reason explained in Section 3.1.1.1. Besides, the production process of low-alloyed steel used in the construction of 1-3 MW wind turbine assembly raked as the second important contributor of IR and FTA. The production process of polyamide injection reinforced plastic glass fibre (main component of wind turbine blade whose capacity larger than 1MW¹¹⁶), is another important contributor for the high FD score. The major raw material for glass fibre reinforced plastic production, Nylon6-6, is very fossil resources intensive during its production process¹¹⁶. Following the contributor above, the third important contributor to both FTA, IR, FD, and REI is road building process to get access to the wind farm.

Among all the pathways studied, case 2 shows the highest result of FTA, IR, FD and REI, namely 3.61 E-04 mole H⁺_{eq}/MJ H₂, 2.98 E-03 kg U_{235-eq}/MJ H₂, 5.89E-01 MJ/MJ H₂, 3.16 E-09 disease i./MJ H₂, respectively. Case 3 shows the lowest result of these LCIA score, namely 1.37 E-04 mole H⁺_{eq}/MJ H₂, 1.38E-03 kg U_{235-eq}/MJ H₂, 2.68E-01 MJ/MJ H₂, 1.42 E-09 disease i./MJ H₂, respectively.

● *Land use (LU), Minerals and metals depletion (MD), Dissipated water (DW)*

Regarding LU, MD, DW, average French solar electricity supply chain contributes around 62.20 % - 89.66% to the total LCIA score of solar-to-H₂ pathway (case1-case2), ranking as the most important contributor, where most of the LCIA score remained comes from the electrolysis unit plant infrastructure. However, for wind-to-H₂ pathway (case3-case4), 42.21%- 61.87% of the LCIA score to LU, MD, DW comes from electrolysis unit plant infrastructure, which is closely followed by the contribution from average French wind electricity supply chain.

Construction of the PV panel mounting system will occupy large land area, which is the major contributor to the high LU score¹¹⁶ of the average French solar electricity supply chain. Besides, A lot of zinc is the consumed during the construction of the PV panel mounting system, which explains the high MD score of the average French solar electricity supply chain. The high DW score of the average French solar electricity supply chain is due to the massive multi-Si PV panel production and importation from China¹³³. Multi-Si wafer production (basic model for multi-Si PV panel) in China is very water consuming¹³³.

Under French average resource availability and technology market mix, the road construction process occupying large land area, thus leading to the high LU score of the average French wind electricity supply chain. For current technology in French, Zinc coating is massively applied to wind turbine tower to against corrosion, which lead to the high MD score of the average French wind electricity supply chain. Regarding DW, the production process of polyamide injection reinforced plastic glass fibre used in wind turbine blade and the low-alloyed steel used in the wind turbine tower contribute equally to the high DW of the average French wind electricity supply chain. Nylon6-6, major raw material for glass fibre reinforced plastic production, is very water consumption intensive during its production process¹¹⁶. So is the same for the production process of low-alloyed steel production under current French context¹¹⁶ as discussed in Section 3.1.1.1.

Regarding the electrolysis unit plant infrastructure, most of the DW score is contributed from the concrete production process, which can be furtherly attributed to the water consumption intensive extraction process of cement production raw material ranked by contribution to DW score¹³³: clinker (Limestone rotary kiln calcination), gravel (extracted from river bed), and sand (extracted from river bed) production under current French context. Besides, to produce the clinker for the electrolysis unit cement foundation production, the limestone rotary kiln calcination is limestone consumption intensive. And the limestone production will consume a lot of zinc¹³³, which explain the high MD score of the electrolysis unit plant infrastructure. Regarding LU, the large amount of sand consumed in the production of electrolysis unit concrete foundation explains the reason of the high LU score of the electrolysis unit plant infrastructure, which is followed by the contribution from limestone consumption during clinker production and the transportation of cement in turn.

Among all the pathways studied, case 2 shows the highest result of LU, MD, DW, namely 4.02 kg Soil Organic/MJ H₂, 6.10 E-06 kg Sb_{-eq}/MJ H₂, 3.11E-02 m³/MJ H₂, respectively. Case 3 shows the lowest result of these LCIA score, namely 4.16 E-01 kg Soil Organic/MJ H₂, 2.11 E-06 kg Sb_{-eq}/MJ H₂, 5.79E-3 m³/MJ H₂, respectively.

● *Ozone layer depletion (OLD)*

Regarding OLD, the electrolysis unit plant infrastructure contributes around 51.9% -64.3% to the total LCIA score of solar-to-H₂ pathway (case1-case2) and wind-to-H₂ pathway group (case3-case4), ranking as the most important contributor. In case1 and case3, where PEM electrolyser is applied in the solar-to-H₂ pathway and wind-to-H₂ pathway, 13.2% and 21.6% of the total LCIA score comes from the production, transportation, and EoL of the PEM electrolysis stack. The remaining LCIA score in solar-to-H₂ pathway and wind-to-H₂ pathway are mainly contributed by French national average solar and wind electricity supply chain, respectively.

With similar reason discussed in GWP, the production of aluminium wrought alloy used in PV panel mounting system, Chinese multi-Si and mono-Si PV panels production and importation process contribute equally to the higher OLD score of the French solar electricity supply chain. Again, like GWP, the main contributor of the high OLD score of electrolysis unit plant infrastructure to FIA, FD, REI mainly come from the production process of clinker (basic raw material for concrete production), where the cement and clinker transportation process, the heavy fuel oil and petroleum coke burned in clinker production, diesel burning in the production of cement and clinker rank as the main contributors in turn regarding the contribution amount.

The road construction process, with the reason discussed in GWP, explain the high OLD score of the average French wind electricity supply chain. The production process of low-alloyed steel used in the wind turbine tower production under current French context¹¹⁶ is the second important contributor to the OLD score of the average French wind electricity supply chain with the reason discussed in Section 3.1.1.1. Among all the pathways studied, case 1 shows the highest result of LU, MD, DW, namely 4.03 E-09 kg CFC-11/MJ H₂. Case 4 shows the lowest result of these LCIA score, namely 1.99 E-09 kg CFC-11/MJ H₂.

● *Carcinogenic effect (CE)*

Regarding CE, the average French solar and wind electricity supply chain contributes around 69.4% - 82.7% to the total LCIA score of solar-to-H₂ pathway (case1-case2) and wind-to-H₂ pathway (case3-case4), respectively, ranking as the most important contributor. The remaining LCIA score in solar-to-H₂ pathway and wind-to-H₂ pathway are mainly contributed by electrolysis unit plant infrastructure, respectively.

Under current French context, primary aluminium wrought alloy is massively used in for PV panels mounting system, where the major technology for aluminium wrought alloy production in French is refining the aluminium oxide (made by red mud from bauxite digestion) through the Hall-Héroult process¹¹⁶. Hall-Héroult process is very electricity consumption intensive and bauxite digestion process is very pollutant emission intensive, thus explaining the reason for the high CE score of the French average solar electricity supply chain. Besides, PV panels mounting system consumed a lot of reinforcing steel, which is mostly made from low-alloyed steel under current French context. The production process of low-alloyed steel used in the PV panels mounting system¹¹⁶ is the second important contributor to the high CE score of the French average solar electricity supply chain with the reason discussed in Section 3.1.1.1.

The production process of the low-alloyed steel and chromium steel used in the wind turbine tower is the main contributor to the high CE score of the average French wind electricity supply chain with the reason discussed in Section 3.1.1.1. The production process of low-alloyed steel under current French context. clinker (basic raw material for concrete production) from limestone rotary kiln calcination process, is the main contributor of the high CE score of the water electrolysis unit plant infrastructure with the reason discussed above and in Section 3.1.1.1. Among all the pathways studied, case 2 shows the highest result of CE, namely $1.54 \text{ E-}09 \text{ kg CTUh/MJ H}_2$. Case 3 shows the lowest result of these LCIA score, namely $1.30 \text{ E-}09 \text{ kg CTUh /MJ H}_2$.

● *Special focus: contribution from AE and PEM electrolysis stack*

As we can see from Fig. 3.7 that, during water electrolysis H_2 production process, applying PEM electrolyser stack has a much lower environmental impact than AE electrolysis stack regarding all the impact categories studied by this research, except OLD. The production process of manganese (the critical component of the cathode material), mainly as electrothermal and electrolysis treatment of manganese ore is pollutant emission intensive in terms of NH_3 , HCl, VOC and heavy metals¹¹⁶. This explaining the high CE score of the AE electrolysis stack production. Besides, the production process of 99.5% Nickel, another critical material of the electrode, made from hydrometallurgical and the pyrometallurgical nickel ore refining¹¹⁶, will emitted large amounts of dust, containing PM10 and VOC¹¹⁶. Thus, explain the high LCIA score of AE electrolysis stack production in terms of GWP, FTA, POC and REI. The underground nickel ore mining infrastructure construction, and heat consumption during the ore mining process, explains the high score of AE electrolysis stack production in terms of FD, LU and MD. Besides, large amount of electricity is consumed during the AE electrolysis stack assembling explain the high IR and DW score, due to the reason discussed in Section 3.1.1.1. Regarding OLD, production of the solid polymer electrolyte from trichloromethane is very CFC emission intensive, explaining the reason of the high OLD score of PEM electrolysis stack production.

As shown in Fig. 3.6 and the supplementary materials, AE electrolysis stack contribute 19.12% and 34.14% in the total FTA score of case 2 and case 4 respectively. And PEM electrolysis stack contribute 13.2% and 21.6% in the total FTA score of case 1 and case 3 respectively. Contribution from the production, transportation, and EoL treatment process of AE electrolysis stack in the total score of IR, POC, REI and CE for case2 and case4 is small but not neglectable. For the LCIA score of the other categories, in the 4 RE-to- H_2 pathways studied, the contribution from both the AE and PEM electrolysis stack is neglectable.

Figure 3.7: LCIA result comparison between PEM electrolysis stack and AE electrolysis stack.

3.1.2.2 Scenario variation and further comparison

• Comparison with other researches

Figure 3.8: LCIA result comparison among RE-to-H₂ pathway, arithmetic mean value obtained through Monte Carlo simulation.

Fig. 3.8 show the LCIA result comparison among all the 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways. It's clear that whether from the view of comprehensive trade-off to all impact categories studied or only considering the GWP, water electrolysis H₂ production with French average wind electricity through PEM electrolysis unit is the optional choices among all the four RE-to-H₂ pathways studied.

Figure 3.9: LCIA result comparison among RE-to-H₂ pathway with scenario variation.

In RE-to-H₂ pathway, this research applies the 40 MPa concrete in the building of the electrolysis unit foundation. The total mass of the electrolysis unit, i.e., stack, electronics, pumps, safety equipment, is huge, which could be up to 9.6 t taking the PEM electrolysis unit as example²⁵. A foundation with high

compressive strength is required for the stable installation of the electrolysis unit on the ground. Fig. 3.9 a) shows the LCIA result of wind-to-H₂ pathway using PEM electrolysis unit built on 20MPa concrete foundation, which is compared with the LCIA result of case3. Fig.3.9 also shows the result of wind-to-H₂ pathway using PEM electrolysis unit under the maximum and minimum capacity factor of French wind turbine, as well as the LCIA result of two solar-to-H₂ pathways with maximum annual solar irradiance in France. The average capacity factor of French wind turbine, both for onshore and off-shore used in the LCI of arithmetic mean value shown in Fig. 3.6, is already close to the maximum capacity factor. Thus, water electrolysis H₂ production with wind electricity under the maximum capacity factor only reduce less than 7% to each impact categories compared with the LCIA result of case3. Transferring the 40MPa concrete foundation to 20MPa concrete foundation will lead to a higher reduce of the environmental impact: 1.47%-2.52% reduction to CE, OLD, and REI; 7.03%-13.96% reduction to GWP, FTA, IR, POC, FD, MD, and DW. However, LU will increase around 10.68 %, due to the higher sand consumption during the production of 20MPa cement ¹¹⁶. Although under maximum annual solar irradiance, the LCIA score to solar-to-H₂ pathway will be reduced around 20% compared with the result of case2, the environmental impact of solar-to-H₂ pathways is still bigger than all the wind-to-H₂ pathways studied in Fig. 3.9 a).

Fig. 3.9 b) compares the result of case2 and case3 with the PEM water electrolysis H₂ production through Norwegian and French electricity grid (94.1% Norwegian electricity generated by hydro power and 70% French electricity comes from PWR as stated above ¹¹⁶), as well as European-average electricity from ENTSO-E. Compared with Norwegian, French, and ENTSO-E electricity, French average wind electricity is still a better choice for water electrolysis H₂ production, in terms of most impact categories studied. Water electrolysis H₂ production with Norwegian electricity is most comparable to the French average wind electricity water electrolysis regarding most of the impact categories studied despite the high water footprint of Norwegian electricity production, it will reduce the CE significantly compared with case3. Applying the French electricity in water electrolysis H₂ production will also reduce the CE (36.59%) of PEM water electrolysis compared with case3, but will induce a huge increasing in terms of IR, OLD, REI, and DW (981.52%-19188.59%), together with a moderate increasing in terms of all the other categories (32.36%-190.22%). Applying the ENTSO-E electricity in water electrolysis H₂ production will increase the all the impact categories (34.32%-1688.00%) of PEM water electrolysis compared with case3. Case2 embodied with huge MD and LU score as explained in Section 3.1.2.1., applying the Norwegian, French, and ENTSO-E electricity in AE water electrolysis will reduce the MD and LU (42.64%-76.78%) significantly compared with the LCIA result of case2.

3.1.3 Comparison among CH₄-to-H₂ and RE-to-H₂ pathway

The LCIA score of CH₄-to-H₂ and RE-to-H₂ pathways studied by this research is furtherly compared in Fig. 3.10. We can see from Fig. 3.10 that, under current French average resource availability and technology market mix, compared with RE-to-H₂ pathways, the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway is endowing with much FD (47.9%-82.22% higher), and OLD (70.52%-83.9% higher), whatever the reformer type, WGSR type, the CCS technologies and corresponding carbon capture ratio. Compared with all the RE-to-H₂ pathways, in terms of GWP, CH₄-to-H₂ pathway with 98% carbon capture ratio will achieve 10% lower LCIA score for ATR technology and around 10% higher LCIA score for SMR technology. The GWP of CH₄-to-H₂ pathway without CCS is 40%-70% higher than the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway. Instead, the score of FTA (13.27%-81.72% higher), CE (72.45%-87.43% higher), POC (10.94%-74% higher), REI (34.95%-94.71% higher), LU (7.24%-99% higher), MD (30.89%-96.42% higher), of the 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways is bigger than all the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, whatever the electricity source or Electrolysis technology used. When replacing the nuclear dominated FR electricity with Norwegian and Danish electricity in methane reforming H₂ production, IR of CH₄-to-H₂ pathway will gradually decrease and become 8.78%-41.56% lower than result of the 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways, with the reason explained in Section 3.1.1.1. For DW, the score for 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways will be 8.01%-96.26% higher than all the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, except the case7 in CH₄-to-H₂ pathway consuming hydropower dominated Norwegian electricity whose DW score is 7.63% higher than the score of case3 in RE-to-H₂ pathways.

From the angle of comprehensive trade-off to all impact categories studied, under current French average resource availability and technology market mix, three H₂ production technologies, (1) the SMR of French methane mix with HTLT WGSR and MDEA CCS(98% capture ratio) with wind

dominated Danish electricity, (2) the SMR of French methane mix with HTLT WGSR and MDEA CCS(98% capture ratio) with hydro dominated Norwegian electricity, (3) water electrolysis H₂ production through PEM electrolysis unit using the French average wind electricity are the optimal pathway among all pathways studied.

Figure 3.10: LCIA result comparison among RE-to-H₂ and CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, arithmetic mean value obtained through Monte Carlo simulation.

3.2 Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis

3.2.1 Methane reforming H₂ production

3.2.1.1 Sensitivity of LCIA result to LCI parameters

Figure 3.11: Sensitivity of LCIA score to life cycle parameters in case 7 of a) Sobol indices, b) LCIA score deviation due to life cycle parameters' uncertainty. Name of life cycle parameters corresponding to the meaning as shown in Table 2.5.

Fig. 3.11 shows the first-order indices Sobol indices, namely S1 indices, of LCIA score to each life cycle parameter in case 7, namely the SMR HTLT H₂ production with MDEA CCS and 98% CCS ratio. We can see that among all the life cycle parameters, under average French resource availability and technology mix, variation of each impact categories LCIA score is almost totally induced by the uncertainty of bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid. Besides, we can also observe from Fig. 3K b) that variation of all the life cycle parameters under the French context is so small that they will induce very small amount of uncertainty to most of impact categories. Only the variation of the bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid 2019 will leads to a 2%, 3%, 7% variation to the LU, REI, DW respectively, with the reason explained in Section 3.1.1.1. However, the Sobol indices of life cycle parameter and the corresponding uncertainty induced in each impact categories' score will vary among different H₂ production pathway as shown in Fig. 3.12 and Fig.3.13 below.

Figure 3.12: Variation of Sobol indices to each life cycle parameter studied among different H₂ production pathway and impact categories. Name of the life cycle parameters corresponding to the same meaning as shown in Table 2.5.

Among the HT SMR pathways (case 1 - 4), HTLT SMR pathways (case 5 - 8), and HTLT ATR pathways (case 9 - 12), with the increasing of carbon capture ratio, electricity consumption during the CCS operation process is gradually increasing. Especially for the cases applying VPSA CCS technology, which consume much more electricity compared with MDEA CCS technology under the same carbon capture ratio. And with the magnitude of CCS operation electricity consumption increasing, its variation also increasing. Thus, leading to an increasing Sobol indices of CCS operation electricity consumption for each impact category shown in Fig. 3.12, when the carbon capture ratio inside HT SMR group (case 1 - 4), HTLT SMR group (case 5 - 8), and HTLT ATR group is increasing. For IR, and FD, the Sobol indices of CCS operation electricity consumption is becomes larger than the Sobol indices of bio-CH₄

injection ratio in French national gas grid. Thus, the variation of CCS operation electricity consumption contributes most to the uncertainty of IR and FD score in pathways applying VSPA CCS technology. A higher carbon capture ratio also indicates more demand for the CO₂ transportation process due to more CO₂ captured. Thus, the CO₂ transport distance will have more influence on the final LCIA result as shown by the increasing Sobol indices, especially for CE and POC. Other impact categories studied but not shown in Fig. 3.12 show similar pattern to MD, where the uncertainty of the LCIA score is almost totally induced by the uncertainty of bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid. The result of S1 indices of each life cycle parameter and magnitude of LCIA score's uncertainty induced by all life cycle parameters' variation to each impact categories for case1 – case12 can be found in the supplement materials.

3.2.1.2 LCIA result uncertainty

Figure 3.13: Uncertainty to each impact categories induced by life cycle parameter variation in CH₄-to-H₂ pathway.

We can see from Fig.3.13 that, DW, REI and LU have larger uncertainties than the other impact categories. Among all the pathways studied, CV for DW, REI, and LU vary among 1.35 E-01 to 4.78 E-02, 3.06 E-02 to 2.31 E-02, 2.65 E-02 to 1.88 E-02, respectively. And CV for other impact categories is generally smaller than 2.0 E-02. The main contributors to this high uncertainty have been identified in Fig. 3.11 and 3.12. CV from each impact categories' score is determined by the main contributor to LCIA score (μ) and to the LCIA score deviation (SD) for each category discussed in Section 3.1.1.1 and 3.2.1.1, respectively. Among GWP, FTA, IR, REI, LU, DW, impact categories' CV of some H₂ production pathway is especially high, this is mainly because the LCIA score μ for these pathways is very small compared to the μ for other pathway inside the same impact categories, but the difference of LCIA score's SD among each pathway inside the same impact category is very minimal. Supplementary materials contain the detailed information to LCIA score uncertainty (namely P10, P25, P50, P75, P95, SD and μ) of all the 12 pathways studied among each impact categories.

3.2.2 Water electrolysis H₂ with renewable electricity

3.2.2.1 Sensitivity of LCIA result to LCI parameters

Figure 3.14: Sensitivity of LCIA score to life cycle parameters in case 3 of a) Sobol indices, b) LCIA score deviation due to life cycle parameters' uncertainty. Name of life cycle parameters corresponding to the same meaning as shown in Table 2.6.

Fig. 3.14 shows the First-order indices (S1 indices), of LCIA score to each life cycle parameter in case 3 of RE-to-H₂ pathway, namely the water electrolysis H₂ through PEM electrolyser using French average wind electricity. For each impact category studied, under average French resource availability and technology mix, 33%-65% of the LCIA score variation (or in other word, uncertainty) comes from the uncertainty to electrolysis unit global efficiency. The remaining LCIA score variation mainly comes from the uncertainty of wind turbine life time (contribute 53% to the CE variation, and 8% to 29% to the LCIA score variation of all the other 11 impact categories), onshore wind turbine capacity factor (12%-19% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied), electrolysis unit BOP lifetime (4%-11% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied), and share of wind turbine assembly with >3MW capacity in French average onshore wind turbine market (1%-9% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied).

However, under current French context, according to Fig. 3.14 b), uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced by the life cycle parameter variation is still small. For all impact categories, LCIA score uncertainty induced from the variation of electrolysis unit global efficiency is around 6-7%. Uncertainty of CE induced from the variation of French onshore wind turbine capacity factor is 8%. Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced by the remaining life cycle parameter, is below 5%. Compared with these results for case3, the result of S1 indices to each life cycle parameter and magnitude of LCIA score's uncertainty induced by all life cycle parameters to each impact categories are very similar for case4, namely the water electrolysis H₂ production with AE unit with French average wind electricity. The result of same context as shown in Fig. 3.14 for case4 can be found in the supplement material.

Figure 3.15: Sensitivity of LCIA score to life cycle parameters in case 2 of a) Sobol indices, b) LCIA score deviation due to life cycle parameters' uncertainty. Name of life cycle parameters corresponding to the same meaning as shown in Table 2.6.

Fig. 3.15 shows the First-order indices, namely the S1 indices, of LCIA score to each life cycle parameter in case 2 of RE-to-H₂ pathway, namely the water electrolysis H₂ through AE electrolyser using French average solar electricity. For each impact category studied, under average French resource availability and technology mix, 38%-50% of the LCIA score variation (or in other word, uncertainty)

comes from the uncertainty to French average annual solar irradiation available on the PV panels. 24%-30% of the LCIA score variation comes from the average performance ratio of PV panels. The remaining LCIA score variation mainly comes from the uncertainty of PV panel life time (contribute 19%-28% to the variation of CE, DW, and LU; and 6% to 16% to the LCIA score variation of all the other 8 impact categories), electrolysis unit global efficiency (6%-12% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied), nominal maximum power of the PV panels (1%-6% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied).

In French average solar electricity supply chain, more life cycle parameters are identified with larger uncertainties compared with the French average wind electricity supply chain. Thus, the magnitude of LCIA score's uncertainty induced by different life cycle parameters' uncertainty to each impact categories in solar-to-H₂ pathway are much larger than in the wind-to-H₂ pathway. For all impact categories, LCIA score uncertainty induced from the variation of French average annual solar irradiation is around 13-16%; Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced from the average performance ratio of PV panels is 10-13%. Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced from the PV panel life time is 6-13%. Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced by the remaining life cycle parameter, is below 7%. Compared with the results for case2, the result of same content as shown in Fig. 3.15 are very similar for case1, namely the water electrolysis H₂ production with PEM unit with French average solar electricity. The result of S1 indices to each life cycle parameter and magnitude of LCIA score's uncertainty induced by all life cycle parameters' variation to each impact categories for case1 - case4 can be found in the supplement materials.

3.2.2.2 LCIA result uncertainty

Figure 3.16: Uncertainty to each impact categories induced by life cycle parameter variation in RE-to-H₂ pathway.

We can see from Fig.3.16 that, due to more life cycle parameters identified with larger uncertainties in French average solar electricity supply chain as stated above, for all impact categories studied, LCIA score's CV of solar-to-H₂ pathway is 9.57%-16.44% higher compared with LCIA score's uncertainty of wind-to-H₂ pathway. Due to the main contributor to LCIA score and to of LCIA score deviation for each category discussed in Section 3.1.2.1 and 3.2.2.1, respectively, impact categories' CV in case1 is 0.16%-3.76% larger than the result in case2, for all the impact categories studied, except for OLD. OLD ' CV in case1 is 2.21% smaller than case2. Each impact categories' CV for case3 and case4 is also very comparable to each other, where the difference of each impact categories' CV between case3 and case4 is smaller than 1.3%. It's clearly from Fig.3.16 and Fig.3.13 that, CV for almost all the impact category score of RE-to-H₂ pathway is larger than the CV for the corresponding impact category score of CH₄-to-H₂ pathway. Supplementary materials contain the detailed information to LCIA score uncertainty (namely P10, P25, P50, P75, P95, SD and μ) of all the 4 pathways studied among each impact categories.

3.3 Guidance on improving life cycle sustainability of H₂ production

According to the LCIA score interpretation based on unit process contribution, findings discovered from comparison with other research results, as well as corresponding sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, this research propose the following suggestions aiming at improving the sustainability and renewability for both CH₄-to-H₂ and RE-to-H₂ technology under French national average resource availability and technology market mix.

3.3.1 Methane reforming H₂ production

● *Fossil NG supply chain in France*

Fossil NG reforming will still be the major technology for H₂ production in France during the first half of 20th century. To decarbonizing and depolluting the Fossil NG reforming H₂ production sector in France, one of the most important strategies is to search and shifting to a more cleaning NG source rather than importing massive NG from Russia (currently 27% in FR total NG consumption), whose production and transportation process is resource consumption and emission intensive in terms of CO₂ and other pollutants. Only taking the environmental impact into considerations, NG imported from Russia should rank as the first priority to be substituted by the bio-CH₄ or renewable-power-to-methane technologies among all the fossil NG sources in French.

● *Bio-CH₄ supply chain in France*

France aims to reach 10% renewable methane (almost all is bio-CH₄) in the total NG consumption of France by 2030, namely 10 % of should be. Currently the bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid is still minor as discussed in Section 3.1.1.1, so is the same to the annual amount of H₂ produced from bio-CH₄ in France. However, to fulfil the decarbonization target to the H₂ sector set by the ‘hydrogen deployment plan for the energy transition’^{11, 12}, in the following decade, amount of H₂ production through bio-CH₄ reforming will receive great significant increasing.

Currently, bio-CH₄ is mostly produced from AD in France as discussed in Section 2.3.1. If allocating the environmental influence of AD plant construction and operation to bio-CH₄ rather than food and agricultural sector¹¹⁸, bio-CH₄ production and upgrading will cause huge environmental influence.

To improving the sustainability of bio-CH₄ supply chain in France, one of the most important strategies is to developing new biogas upgrading process and innovate the most widely used biogas upgrading process: amine scrubbing, whose upgrading catalyst (2 wt % potassium iodide solution) production is very water consuming¹¹⁶.

For the biomass building materials already applied in the AD plant infrastructure, the recyclable biomass should be taken as priority and ensure the recycling process during the end-of-life treatment of the plant infrastructure to reducing the life cycle land usage in bio-CH₄ production. Besides, special focus should be paid on innovation and regulation on storage tank of AD substrate and digestate, to reduce the pollutant escape, i.e., ammonia.

● *Methane reforming H₂ production and CCS application*

Regarding the plant infrastructure of methane reforming H₂ production, for both ATR and SMR methane reforming plant, plant constructor should highlight the usage of chromium and low-alloyed steel with a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. And try to substitute the iron infrastructure with other innovative materials with lower environmental impact, i.e., laminated timber especially made from recycled paper or waste biomass. For the biomass building materials already applied in the plant infrastructure, one should also take the recyclable materials as priority and ensure the recycling process during the end-of-life treatment of the plant infrastructure to reducing the life cycle land usage in H₂ production. Besides, to reduce the rare metals consumption, innovation should also focus on structure and material science of metallic material splicing (welding as technology most widely used currently) to reduce the zinc-brazing solder consumption. Regarding the catalyst used in methane reforming H₂ production, special attention should be paid to innovate more environmentally friendly precious material recycling method to improving the recycling ratio.

H₂ production efficiency for ATR technology is higher than SMR technology, however, in the prize of higher electricity consumption and NO_x emission from the reformer furnace. Thus, its logical to apply denitrification equipment to the furnace of ATR reformer to control the pollutant emission. Besides, for region with rich hydraulic resources, hydroelectricity can be a priority to electricity from average FR electricity grid during the operation of H₂ production plant and related CCS facilities, to further reduce the environmental impact of H₂ production.

Regarding CCS technology, electricity consumption during CCS operation contributes much more environmental impact than the corresponding CCS facilities construction process. If applying CCS to methane reforming H₂ production plant, plant constructor should focus on CCS technology with higher carbon capture efficiency under the same electricity consumption, where innovation on improving the

carbon capture efficiency is also of high importance to decarbonizing and depolluting the CCS process during methane reforming H_2 production.

3.3.2 Water electrolysis H_2 with renewable electricity

● *French average solar electricity supply chain*

For the solar electricity supply chain under current French context, lots of PV panels, especially the multi-Si and mono-Si panels, is manufactured, assembled in China, and then imported to France and Europe. Production and manufacture the Si panels and related materials, e.g., solar gride silicon and silicon ingot is very fossil energy and water consumption intensive and emission intensive in terms of CO_2 , NO_x , and other pollutant¹¹⁶. However, under the renewable and sustainable transition flourishing in China¹⁶⁹⁻¹⁷¹, the environmental impact embodied in PV panels transported from China is gradually decreasing¹¹⁶. When assembling the PV mounting system, to reducing the life cycle GWP, OLD, FTA, CE and MD score of French average solar electricity production, PV plan constructors should highlight the zinc and aluminum consumption extensive component which has a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. Special attention should be paid to ensure the recycling process during the end-of-life treatment of these component. Desulfurization and denitrification device could be added to the bauxite digester to reduce the CE embodied in aluminum production. During the PV plant operation, good education and training should applied to the operators to achieve higher performance ratio and PV panel lifetime with other site-specific strategy, which is quite important to achieve a lower environmental impact regarding all the impact categories studied. Besides, innovation should specially focus on improving the irradiance tracing system and PV panels site distribution, thus to fulfill lower LU score with the same solar energy produced.

● *French average wind electricity supply chain*

Chromium steel and low-alloyed steel is massively consumed in the wind turbine tower construction. Similar suggestions regarding the steel and low-alloyed steel sector depolluting proposed in section 3.3.1.1 is also recommended here to improving French average wind electricity supply chain. Copper is another critical material used in the wind turbine tower construction. Besides highlighting the copper product with a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. Desulfurization device is recommended form the major copper production technology in EU, to reduce the FTA score embodied in copper production. Developing biomass based or other more environmental friendly nylon 6-6 alternatives will reduce the DW and FD in wind turbine blade production effectively. To reducing the MD score, regarding the zinc coating massively consumed for wind turbine tower anti-corrosion, similar suggestions discussed in French average solar electricity supply chain is recommended here. Innovation on less electricity intensive method of wind turbine assembling, mounting and end-of-life (EoL) removal of the wind turbine will achieve a lower DW and FTA sore for French average wind electricity supply chain. To fulfill a more environmentally friendly access to the wind power plant from densely populated area, in terms of OLD, LU, GWP, FTA, IR, FD, and REI, wind plant builder in charge of relative road building should highlight the biomass base alternatives to fossil basic asphalt. Special focus should be paid on transportation distance of road construction raw material and diesel consumption efficiency during road construction. During the electrolysis unit operation, good education and training should applied to the operators to achieve higher wind turbine lifetime, which is quite important to achieve a lower environmental impact regarding all the impact categories studied.

● *Water electrolysis unit and electrolysis H_2 production*

High population density area with high wind resource should be the top priority area to fulfill replacement of the NG reforming dominated H_2 production with water electrolysis H_2 production through wind energy. Regarding the AE stack, water electrolysis H_2 producer should focus on electrode manganese and 99.5% nickel with a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. The electrothermal manganese ore reformer, as the major manganese production technology, should apply denitrification and other depolluting device to reduce the high NH_3 , HCl, VOC emission from the reformer. During the manganese ore reforming, heat from renewable biomass source should become the first choice rather than the fossil-based heat. Similar strategies are also recommended to the major technology for 99.5% nickel production in EU: pyrometallurgical nickel ore refining to reduce the PM10 and VOC emission. Innovation on less electricity intensive method of AE electrolysis assembling, mounting and end-of-life (EoL) removal of the electrolysis unit

will achieve a lower DW and FTA score for AE stack assembling. Innovation on biomass material based trichloromethane alternatives should receive further attention to reduce the OLD score embodied PEM stack production. Special focus should be paid on improving the stack efficiency, i.g., innovation on temperature optimization technology from the proton exchange membrane in PEM electrolysis unit, the addition of more efficient electrolyte and electrocatalysts. During the electrolysis unit operation, good education and training should be applied to the operators to achieve higher electrolysis efficiency and BOP life time, which is quite important to achieve a lower environmental impact regarding all the impact categories studied.

This research identifies the following measures to decarbonizing and depolluting of electrolysis unit plant infrastructure, e.g., the electrolyser BOP, H₂ compressor. When building the concrete foundation, water electrolysis H₂ producer should choose the concrete with the lowest compressive strength that meet the ground stabilization requirement of the electrolysis unit. Especially, to reduce the GWP, POC, CE, OLD, and REI score, H₂ producer should focus on the concrete with a high recycling rate regarding the concrete production raw material (gravel and sand) and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. Besides, transportation distance of the concrete should receive special optimization. And hydro power should be first used in the concrete production for regions rich in water resources. Innovation should specially focus on improving the efficiency of major clinker production technology in EU: limestone rotary kiln calcination. Heat from renewable biomass source should become the first choice rather than the fossil-based heat during the limestone rotary kiln calcination process.

Chapter 4. Conclusions and perspectives

From the angle of the average resource availability and technology market share in France in 2019, this research analyze and compare the environmental influence of methane reforming H₂ production technology and water electrolysis H₂ production with renewable electricity. With the corresponding parametric LCA model built in BW2 based *lca_algebraic* library, towards 11 impact categories, this research performs the first detail and holistic SA and UA regarding all the foreground and background life cycle parameters involved in the H₂ production life cycle. 12 CH₄-to-H₂ pathway and 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways were analysed base on different technical details and life cycle hypothesis. According to the LCIA score interpretation based on unit process contribution, findings discovered from comparison with other research results, as well as SA and UA, this research also propose the guidelines and suggestions towards improving the life cycle sustainability of H₂ production pathways analysed.

Under current average French context, the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway is endowing with much FD (47.9%-82.22% higher), and OLD (70.52%-83.9% higher), whatever the technical details. Compared with all RE-to-H₂ pathways, in terms of GWP, CH₄-to-H₂ pathway with 98% carbon capture ratio will achieve 10% lower LCIA score for ATR technology and around 10% higher LCIA score for SMR technology. The GWP of CH₄-to-H₂ pathway without CCS is 40%-70% higher than the RE-to-H₂ pathway.

Instead, the score of FTA (13.27%-81.72% higher), CE (72.45%-87.43% higher), POC (10.94%-74% higher), REI (34.95%-94.71% higher), LU (7.24%-99% higher), MD (30.89%-96.42% higher), of the 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways is higher than all the CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, whatever the electricity source or electrolysis technology used. When replacing the nuclear dominated FR electricity with hydro dominated Norwegian or wind dominated Danish electricity in methane reforming H₂ production, IR of CH₄-to-H₂ pathway will gradually decrease and become 8.78%-41.56% lower than result of the 4 RE-to-H₂ pathways.

From the angle of comprehensive trade-off to all impact categories studied, under current French average resource availability and technology market mix, three H₂ production technologies, (1) the SMR of French methane mix with HTLT WGS and MDEA CCS(98% capture ratio) with wind dominated Danish electricity, (2) the SMR of French methane mix with HTLT WGS and MDEA CCS(98% capture ratio) with hydro dominated Norwegian electricity, (3) water electrolysis H₂ production through PEM electrolysis unit using the French average wind electricity are the optimal pathway among all pathways studied.

Among all the life cycle parameters, under average French resource availability and technology mix, variation of each impact categories LCIA score is almost totally induced by the uncertainty of bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid. Under current French context, variation of all the life cycle parameters induce very small amount of uncertainty to most of impact categories. Only the variation of the bio-CH₄ injection ratio in French national gas grid 2019 will leads to a 2%, 3%, 7% variation to the LU, REI, DW respectively.

For the LCIA result to water electrolysis H₂ through PEM electrolyser using French average wind electricity, under average French resource availability and technology mix, 33%-65% of the LCIA score uncertainty to each impact categories studied comes from the uncertainty to electrolysis unit global efficiency. The remaining LCIA score variation mainly comes from the uncertainty of wind turbine life time (contribute 53% to the CE variation, and 8% to 29% to the LCIA score variation of all the other 11 impact categories), onshore wind turbine capacity factor (12%-19% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied), electrolysis unit BOP lifetime (4%-11% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied), and share of wind turbine assembly with >3MW capacity in French average onshore wind turbine market(1%-9% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied). For all impact categories, LCIA score uncertainty induced from the variation of electrolysis unit global efficiency is around 6-7%. Uncertainty of CE induced from the variation of French onshore wind turbine capacity factor is 8%. Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced by the remaining life cycle parameter, is below 5%. These result, namely the of S1 indices to each life cycle parameter and magnitude of LCIA score uncertainty induced by all life cycle parameters to each impact categories are very similar for the water electrolysis H₂ production with AE unit with French average wind electricity.

For the LCIA result to water electrolysis H₂ through AE electrolyser using French average solar

electricity, under average French resource availability and technology mix, 38%-50% of the LCIA score uncertainty to each impact categories comes from the uncertainty to French average annual solar irradiation available on the PV panels. 24%-30% of the LCIA score variation comes from the average performance ratio of PV panels. The remaining LCIA score variation mainly comes from the uncertainty of PV panel life time (contribute 19%-28% to the variation of CE, DW, and LU; and 6% to 16% to the LCIA score variation of all the other 8 impact categories), electrolysis unit global efficiency (6%-12% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied), nominal maximum power of the PV panels (1%-6% to the LCIA score variation of all impact categories studied). For all impact categories, LCIA score uncertainty induced from the variation of French average annual solar irradiation is around 13-16%; Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced from the average performance ratio of PV panels is 10-13%. Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced from the PV panel life time is 6-13%. Uncertainty to each impact categories' score induced by the remaining life cycle parameter, is below 7%. These result, namely the of S1 indices to each life cycle parameter and magnitude of LCIA score uncertainty induced by all life cycle parameters to each impact categories are very similar for the water electrolysis H₂ production with PEM unit with French average solar electricity.

For CH₄-to-H₂ pathway, only taking the environmental impact into considerations, NG importing from Russia should rank as the first priority to be substituted by the bio-CH₄ or renewable-power-to-methane technologies among all the fossil NG sources in French. One of the most important strategies to improving the H₂ production sustainability is to developing new biogas upgrading process and innovate the most widely used biogas upgrading process: amine scrubbing, whose upgrading catalyst (2 wt % potassium iodide solution) production is very water consuming.

Besides, for both ATR and SMR methane reforming plant, instead of plant constructor should highlight the usage of chromium and low-alloyed steel as well as the refined and processed by renewable electricity. And try to substitute the iron infrastructure with other innovative materials with lower environmental impact, i.e., laminated timber especially made from recycled paper or waste biomass. For the biomass building materials already applied in the plant infrastructure, one should also take the recyclable materials as priority and ensure the recycling process during the end-of-life treatment of the plant infrastructure to reducing the life cycle land usage in H₂ production. Besides, to reduce the rare metals consumption, innovation should also focus on structure and material science of metallic material splicing (welding as technology most widely used currently) to reduce the zinc-brazing solder consumption. Regarding the catalyst used in methane reforming H₂ production, special attention should be paid to innovate more environmentally friendly precious material recycling method to improving the recycling ratio. It is logical to apply denitrification equipment to the furnace of ATR reformer to control the pollutant emission. Besides, for region with rich hydraulic resources, hydroelectricity can be a priority to electricity from average FR electricity grid during the operation of H₂ production plant and related CCS facilities, to further reduce the environmental impact of H₂ production. If applying CCS to methane reforming H₂ production plant, plant constructor should focus on CCS technology with higher carbon capture efficiency under the same electricity consumption.

For solar-to-H₂ pathway, PV plant constructors should highlight the zinc and aluminum consumption extensive component which has a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. Special attention should be paid to ensure the recycling process during the end-of-life treatment of these component. Desulfurization and denitrification device could be added to the bauxite digester to reduce the CE embodied in aluminum production. During the PV plant operation, good education and training should applied to the operators to achieve higher performance ratio and PV panel lifetime together with other site-specific strategy. Besides, innovation should specially focus on improving the irradiance tracing system and PV panels site distribution, thus to fulfill lower LU score with the same solar energy produced.

For wind-to-H₂ pathway, besides highlighting the copper product (largely consumed in wind turbine assembly) with a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. Desulfurization device is recommended form the major copper production technology in EU, to reduce the FTA score embodied in copper production. Developing biomass based or other more environmental friendly nylon 6-6 alternatives will reduce the DW and FD in wind turbine blade production effectively. Innovation on less electricity intensive method of wind turbine assembling, mounting and end-of-life (EoL) removal of the wind turbine will achieve a lower DW and FTA sore for French average wind electricity supply chain. Wind plant builder in charge of relative road building

should highlight the biomass base alternatives to fossil based asphalt. Special focus should be paid on transportation distance of road construction raw material and diesel consumption efficiency during road construction. During the electrolysis unit operation, good education and training should be applied to the operators to achieve higher wind turbine lifetime.

High population density area with high wind resource should be the top priority area to fulfill replacement of the NG reforming dominated H₂ production with water electrolysis H₂ production through wind energy. Regarding the AE stack, water electrolysis H₂ producer should focus on electrode manganese and 99.5% nickel with a high recycling rate and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. The electrothermal manganese ore reformer, as the major manganese production technology, should apply denitrification and other depolluting device to reduce the high NH₃, HCl, VOC emission from the reformer. Innovation on less electricity intensive method of AE electrolysis assembling, mounting and end-of-life (EoL) removal of the electrolysis unit will achieve a lower DW and FTA score for AE stack assembling. Innovation on biomass material based trichloromethane alternatives should receive further attention to reduce the OLD score embodied PEM stack production. Special focus should be paid on improving the stack efficiency, i.e., innovation on temperature optimization technology from the proton exchange membrane in PEM electrolysis unit, the addition of more efficient electrolyte and electrocatalysts. During the electrolysis unit operation, good education and training should be applied to the operators to achieve higher electrolysis efficiency and BIP life time, which is quite important to achieve a lower environmental impact regarding all the impact categories studied.

When building the concrete foundation, water electrolysis H₂ producer should choose the concrete with the lowest compressive strength that meet the ground stabilization requirement of the electrolysis unit. H₂ producer should focus on the concrete with a high recycling rate regarding the concrete production raw material (gravel and sand) and renewable electricity penetration during their production process. Besides, transportation distance of the concrete should receive special optimization. And hydro power should be first used in the concrete production for regions rich in water resources. Innovation should specially focus on improving the efficiency of major clinker production technology in EU: limestone rotary kiln calcination. Heat from renewable biomass source should become the first choice rather than the fossil-based heat during the limestone rotary kiln calcination process.

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